

PREVENT

EMPOWERING CHILDHOOD HEALTH, PREVENTING
OBESITY - GO HEALTHY FOR A BRIGHT FUTURE

**D 2.1: Metrics for childhood obesity and cancer and
identified gaps/barriers to the current policy
frameworks**

**Work Package 2
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Table of contents

List of Tables	4
Executive Summary	4
1.1 <i>Background</i>	5
1.2 <i>Materials and Methods</i>	5
1.2.1. Study selection	6
1.2.2. Eligibility and Exclusion criteria	6
1.2.3. Data Extraction	6
1.2.4. Quality Evaluation	7
1.2.5. Statistical analysis	7
1.3. <i>Results</i>	7
1.3.1. Principal findings	7
1.4. <i>Discussion</i>	13
1.4.1. Comparison with previous studies	13
1.4.2. Biological mechanisms	13
1.4.3. Strengths and limitations	15
2.1. <i>Methodology</i>	16
2.2. <i>Results - Summary characteristics of interventions/policies/strategies from the demo countries</i> 17	
2.2.1. Type and content	17
2.2.2. Health outcome targeted	20
2.2.3. Scale/context, Level and Sector of implementation	21
2.2.4. Target populations and target stakeholders	22
2.2.5. Place and duration of the implementation	23
2.2.6. Material and tools	23
2.2.7. Application of behavioral models and co-creation/participatory methods	24
2.2.8. Legal framework support, enforcement methods, funding	25
2.2.9. Monitoring	26
2.2.10. Barriers	26
2.2.11. Areas of opportunities/ Opportunities for improvement	27
2.3. <i>Results of the short survey on barriers among PREVENT partners</i>	28
2.3.1. Cost/Financing Constraints	28
2.3.2. Social/Cultural Constraints	29
2.3.3. Degree of Acceptability	30
2.3.4. Other Implementation Barriers	31
2.3.5. Areas of opportunities/ Opportunities of improvements	31
3. Metrics for assessing PREVENT's primary interventions	49
4. Conclusions	51
Appendix 2. Short survey Questionnaire to WP2 PREVENT partners	59
Appendix 3. Greece-specific report of the survey results	63
Appendix 4. Spain (Catalonia)-specific report of the survey results	74
Appendix 5. Sweden-specific report of the survey results	90

List of Tables

Table 1. List of identified indicators of childhood or adolescent obesity.....	8
Table 2. Meta-analyses on the association between health-related indicators of childhood or adolescent obesity and adult cancer risk.....	9
Table 3. Subgroup meta-analyses on the association between health-related indicators of childhood or adolescent obesity and adult breast cancer risk by pre- and postmenopausal status	12
Table 4. Main types of barriers/obstacles to the implementation of selected Interventions/Policies/Strategies in Greece, Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden	40
Table 5. Distribution of barriers/obstacles to the implementation of selected interventions/policies/strategies in Greece, Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden by domain of implementation	47
Table 6. Metrics to assess PREVENT's primary interventions.....	49

Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.1 outlines the indicators for assessing the PREVENT interventions and respective engagement policies by addressing two main goals. The first objective is to identify and quantify a list of somatometric indicators, genetic-based attributes, co-morbidities, family and individual health histories, and psychological indices that contribute to pediatric overweight and obesity, and increased risk of cancer in adulthood. This will be achieved through the analysis of *evidence-based clinical research* results. The outcome is a table including: 1) the health-related indicators, 2) their quantified values, 3) the types of cancer that these indicators are related to, 4) the respective cancer risk (short and long-term), and finally 5) the safety margins for preventing cancer. In order to achieve this goal, a meta-analysis is carried out to prioritize the major obesity-related factors that increase the risk of various associated types of cancer.

The second goal is to create a list of indicators, both qualitative and quantitative, for assessing the new PREVENT primary interventions and the respective engagement policies. Various domains, such as economical assessments; social-related validation; user acceptability and sustainability factors; and compatibility with existing politic schemes (frameworks) are taking into consideration. At first, current primary interventions and weight control strategies, both on a European level and internationally, will be examined. Following this, implementation research for **PREVENT** will identify the current barriers and gaps of each intervention policy. A multi-domain and multi-actor gap analysis is foreseen to identify respective limitations, including implementation cost and social constraints, implementation barriers and the degree of acceptability.

1. Metanalysis

1.1 Background

Globally, childhood obesity is a major public health issue related to increased morbidity and mortality, as well as to significant long-term complications, such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus and cancer in later life. The prevalence of childhood obesity and overweight ranges from 15.3% to 25.6% in Europe, while in the United States the respective rate was estimated to be as high as 21.5% in 2020 [1].

Current evidence has linked childhood obesity to major comorbidities in adulthood. About half of patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus have been obese or overweight in childhood [2, 3]. Studies have shown that for each 1kg/m² increase in body mass index (BMI), the risk for diabetes mellitus type 2 increases by 20% [4]. Recent data from the British DIRECT randomized controlled trial have also shown that weight loss of at least 15 kg can reverse type 2 diabetes in 86% of overweight and obese individuals [5]. In the same context, obesity as part of the metabolic syndrome has been associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease [6]. Moreover, a recent meta-analysis study of 2.88 million individuals has shown a statistically significant association between obesity and increased overall mortality rate [7].

There is accumulating evidence focusing on the potential association between childhood obesity and cancer incidence in adulthood. Currently, the International Agency for Research on Cancer has shown significant associations between excess adiposity and 13 types of cancer in adulthood, namely postmenopausal breast, colon and rectum, corpus uteri, esophagus, gallbladder, gastric cardia, kidney, liver, meningioma, multiple myeloma, ovary, pancreas, and thyroid cancer [8]. The pathophysiology of this potential associations includes increased levels of growth factors, such as insulin and insulin-like growth factors, alterations in adipokine levels, such as leptin, visfatin and adiponectin, increased levels of inflammation and oxidative stress, as well as dysregulated microbiome function [9]. Mathematical modelling studies suggest that it takes decades from an initial stem cell mutation to progress to the clinical manifestation of cancer [10]. A recent meta-analysis of observational studies reported that hyperinsulinemia, resulting from high adiposity and subsequent insulin resistance, is a statistically significant risk factor for endometrial cancer [11]. A recent population-based cohort study in Denmark concluded that increased childhood adiposity persisting into adulthood correlated with increased risk for esophageal, gastric and colon cancer in men [12]. Numerous other studies have also reported that obesity seems to be a modifiable risk factor for cancer incidence. However, the majority of published studies focus on the association between adult-onset obesity and the risk of adult cancer.

Acknowledging the current gaps, we conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to explore the association between obesity in children and adolescents and the risk of adult cancer. We searched for all potential indicators of childhood overweight and obesity and examined their association with all types of cancer in adulthood.

1.2 Materials and Methods

The present systematic review and meta-analysis was based on a predefined study protocol (PREVENT project, ID: 101104618) and was performed according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses updated guidelines [13].

1.2.1. Study selection

The Medline database through PubMed, as well as the Excerpta Medica Database (Embase) were in-depth searched for original studies examining the association between childhood obesity and adult cancer risk, from inception up to October 24, 2023. The following key terms were used: (((body AND mass AND index) OR somatometric* OR metric* OR obese OR obesity OR overweight* OR (body AND weight) OR comorbidity OR comorbidities OR distress OR (mental AND health) OR psychological) AND (child OR children OR childhood OR adolescent OR adolescence OR paediatric OR paediatrics OR teenager OR teenagers)) AND ((cancer OR cancers OR malignancy OR malignancies OR tumour OR tumors OR tumor OR tumours OR leukaemia OR leukemia OR lymphoma) AND (adult OR adulthood) AND (risk OR risks OR odds OR incidence))).

The study search was performed by pairs of reviewers who independently and blindly reviewed the literature for potentially eligible studies. The initial selection was based on the titles and abstracts of the studies; thereafter, the full texts were obtained and further evaluated. Any disagreements were resolved by team consensus. The reference lists of all eligible studies were also hand searched for potentially missing publications using the “snowball” procedure. All eligible studies were cross-checked for overlap. In case of complete study overlap, the most recent or largest publication was included in the final set.

1.2.2. Eligibility and Exclusion criteria

Eligible studies were original articles that examined any health-related indicators, namely somatometric indices such as body weight, body mass index or body fat percentage, genetic-based attributes, comorbidities, family and individual health history, as well as psychological indices that correlate pediatric obesity and overweighting with increased cancer risk in adulthood. No restrictions on publication date or language were applied. Only original studies, such as cohort, case-control, nested case-control and cross-sectional studies were included. Reviews, systematic reviews and meta-analyses were excluded. The age range for childhood obesity was defined between 0 and 18 years. Any method for measuring childhood obesity, including waist-to-hip ratio, body mass index or body weight was considered eligible. The diagnosis of cancer should be done in adulthood, namely after 18 years of age with no upper limit. All types of cancer were included in the study selection. Studies examining the association between benign conditions or conditions predisposing to cancer, such as increased breast density were not included in the final selection. Maximally adjusted models were selected in most studies. Studies not reporting effect sizes were excluded.

1.2.3. Data Extraction

The data extraction was performed by pairs of reviewers who worked independently and blindly to each other, using a pre-piloted spreadsheet. The extracted information included: general information for each study, such as first author name, publication year, study period and country of origin, as well as study characteristics, such as study design (e.g. cohort or case-control) completeness and duration of follow-up, type and ascertainment of exposure in childhood, type and ascertainment of cancer, sample size including number of cases and controls or cohort size respectively, childhood mean age and age range, cancer age range and age at cancer diagnosis. Matching factors in case-control studies and adjusting factors were also extracted. Lastly, we extracted the effect estimates (odds ratio, hazard ratio or relative risk) and the respective 95% confidence intervals (CI) in the maximally-adjusted models of each study.

1.2.4. Quality Evaluation

The quality assessment of eligible studies was conducted using the Newcastle-Ottawa Assessment Scale (NOS) [14]. In the “Selection” section of the NOS scale, case-control studies were evaluated on a scale of 0 to 3 points based on definition, representativeness of cases and definition of controls. Cohort studies were evaluated based on representativeness, selection of non-exposed cases, ascertainment of exposure, and whether or not the outcome was present at start. In the “Comparability” section, all studies were given up to 2 points regarding age of the people included and other risk factors that could possibly contribute to the outcome. Lastly, case-control studies were evaluated in the “Exposure” section on a scale of 0 to 1 point based on the ascertainment of exposure, whether or not the same method was used for the ascertainment for both cases and controls, and the non-response rate. On the contrary, cohort studies were evaluated in the “Outcome” section on a scale of 0 to 1 point based on the assessment of outcome, the duration of follow-up with the median range set at 4 years or more, and the adequacy of follow-up with a percentage of 80% considered as adequate follow-up.

1.2.5. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses included pooling of original studies. The statistical analyses were stratified by the type of exposure and type of cancer. Meta-analyses were performed where data were available in more than two studies. Random-effects models were appropriately applied to combine the association estimates of eligible studies with the DerSimonian-Laird estimator for the between-study variance (τ^2), and summary odds ratios (OR) with corresponding 95% CI were calculated. We used the Cochran's Q statistic to assess between-study heterogeneity and I^2 (ranging from 0% to 100%) as the percentage of total variation in effect estimates that is due to heterogeneity rather than sampling error [15]. Different exposure estimates were often used across the studies, such as binary categories, tertiles, quartiles or quintiles, whereas some studies evaluated health-related indicators as linear variables. Opting for comprehensiveness, we stratified the analyses by type of exposure assessment (categorical, linear).

Regarding breast cancer, we further performed sensitivity analyses per age at diagnosis (premenopausal, postmenopausal).

Statistical analyses were performed using Stata software version 14.2 (Stata Corporation, College Station, TX, USA) and p-values ≤ 0.05 were deemed significant.

1.3. Results

1.3.1. Principal findings

The present systematic review and meta-analysis examined potential associations between childhood obesity and different types of cancer in adult life. The systematic search identified 12 distinct indicators as proxies of obesity in childhood or adolescence (for individuals aged <18 years old; Table 1) which were associated with 22 distinct cancer types in adulthood (Figure 1).

Table 1. List of identified indicators of childhood or adolescent obesity.

Adolescent Body Mass Index
Childhood Body Mass Index
Adolescent Body Weight
Childhood Body Weight
Body Surface Area
Childhood BMI and total physical activity (MET-h/wk \geq 78)
Dairy consumption in childhood
Prader-Willi syndrome
Triglyceride levels
Total cholesterol levels
Systolic blood pressure
Glycose levels

Figure 1. Types of adult cancer related to childhood or adolescent obesity

Our findings indicated that most cancer types were associated with childhood or adolescent obesity, with the exception of cervical, lymphoma, multiple myeloma, testicular, lung, stomach and brain cancer. In particular, obesity in childhood was significantly associated with increased risk of esophageal, liver, colorectal, ovarian, pancreatic, bladder, endometrial, thyroid, skin, and renal cancer (Table 2). By contrast, adolescent or childhood overweight was inversely associated with breast cancer. No association was found for hematological cancers (lymphoma, leukemia, and multiple myeloma), as well as for cervical, testicular, lung, stomach and brain cancer. In summary, our findings using various definitions for obesity in childhood and adolescence provide evidence that obesity seems to increase the odds (ration?) for 10 cancer types in adulthood. In terms of the two different age groups, more studies were available for adolescent obesity than childhood obesity, but the results from the latter group were consistent with those from the adolescent studies.

Table 2. Meta-analyses on the association between health-related indicators of childhood or adolescent obesity and adult cancer risk

Indices	Cancer type	N studies	Pooled OR (95% CI)*	Heterogeneity assessment		
				I-squared (%)	Q test	p-value
Adolescent BMI (overweight vs normal)						
	Esophageal	3	1.09 (0.88-1.35)	0.0	1.39	0.50
	Liver	4	1.25 (0.96-1.61)	57.7	7.1	0.07
	Breast	8	0.87 (0.75-1.01)	62.7	18.8	0.009
	Prostate	1	1.30 (1.02-1.65)	-	-	-
	Colorectal	11	1.15 (1.05-1.25)	9.1	11.0	0.36
	Ovarian	3	1.17 (1.00-1.36)	0.0	0.2	0.90
	Pancreatic	4	1.25 (0.98-1.60)	74.7	11.9	0.008
	Bladder	2	1.09 (1.02-1.18)	0.0	0.6	0.44
	Endometrial	1	1.49 (1.24-1.79)	-	-	-
	Cervical	1	1.19 (0.96-1.48)	-	-	-
	Lymphoma	1	1.14 (0.85-1.51)	-	-	-
	Multiple myeloma	3	1.12 (0.84-1.50)	11.0	2.3	0.33
	Leukemia	1	0.95 (0.72-1.26)	-	-	-
	Testicular	3	1.04 (0.85-1.26)	0.0	0.8	0.68
	Thyroid	3	1.22 (0.87-1.73)	0.0	0.7	0.71
	Skin	1	1.51 (1.24-1.83)	-	-	-
	Lung	1	1.06 (0.87-1.29)	-	-	-
	Renal	7	1.32 (1.16-1.50)	0.0	3.9	0.70
	Stomach	3	1.23 (0.82-1.86)	44.2	3.6	0.17
	Brain	1	1.03 (0.86-1.24)	-	-	-
	All cancers	4	1.29 (1.17-1.42)	76.7	12.9	0.005
Adolescent BMI (obese vs normal)						
	Esophageal	4	1.51 (1.04-2.21)	27.3	4.13	0.25
	Liver	3	1.62 (0.73-3.62)	84.9	13.2	0.001
	Breast	8	0.79 (0.57-1.10)	81.6	38.1	<0.0001
	Prostate	2	1.67 (0.62-4.46)	58.4	2.4	0.12
	Colorectal	11	1.08 (1.01-1.15)	45.6	18.4	0.05
	Ovarian	3	1.49 (1.09-2.03)	58.2	4.8	0.09
	Pancreatic	5	2.03 (1.35-3.06)	73.8	15.3	0.004
	Bladder	1	2.10 (1.11-3.97)	-	-	-

Endometrial	7	1.91 (1.43-2.55)	69.3	19.5	0.003
Cervical	1	1.11 (0.66-1.85)	-	-	-
Lymphoma	1	1.28 (0.72-2.28)	-	-	-
Multiple myeloma	1	0.71 (0.17-2.92)	-	-	-
Leukemia	1	1.31 (0.75-2.27)	-	-	-
Testicular	2	1.07 (0.76-1.50)	0.0	0.8	0.37
Thyroid	2	2.30 (1.27-4.18)	0.0	0.6	0.43
Skin	1	1.94 (1.20-3.14)	-	-	-
Lung	2	1.53 (0.81-2.89)	63.8	2.8	0.10
Renal	6	1.98 (1.55-2.53)	0.0	2.7	0.75
Stomach	1	1.23 (0.79-1.91)	-	-	-
Brain	1	0.93 (0.57-1.50)	-	-	-
All cancers	4	1.65 (1.39-1.94)	66.4	8.9	0.03
Adolescent BMI (continuous)					
Bone	1	1.09 (0.36-3.27)	-	-	-
Mouth	1	1.04 (0.71-1.52)	-	-	-
Esophageal	3	1.20 (1.08-1.33)	25.0	2.67	0.26
Liver	4	1.28 (1.14-1.43)	0.0	1.5	0.68
Breast	5	0.88 (0.77-1.02)	85.4	27.4	<0.0001
Prostate	2	1.02 (0.84-1.25)	0.0	0.2	0.65
Colorectal	3	1.10 (0.98-1.25)	0.0	1.0	0.61
Ovarian	3	1.14 (0.90-1.44)	44.1	3.6	0.17
Pancreatic	2	1.84 (1.31-2.59)	27.8	1.4	0.24
Bladder	1	0.80 (0.62-1.03)	-	-	-
Endometrial	1	1.34 (0.94-1.91)	-	-	-
Cervical	1	0.68 (0.37-1.22)	-	-	-
Lymphoma	1	0.99 (0.78-1.25)	-	-	-
Multiple myeloma	1	1.50 (0.97-2.31)	-	-	-
Leukemia	1	1.17 (0.87-1.58)	-	-	-
Adolescent BMI (continuous)					
Testicular	2	1.19 (0.89-1.58)	0.0	0.1	0.71
Thyroid	1	1.17 (0.64-2.14)	-	-	-
Skin	1	1.17 (0.91-1.49)	-	-	-
Lung	3	1.09 (0.97-1.24)	29.2	2.8	0.24
Renal	2	1.06 (1.01-1.11)	0.0	0.0	0.96

	Stomach	1	0.92 (0.51-1.66)	-	-	-
	Brain	1	0.91 (0.52-1.59)	-	-	-
	All cancers	2	1.14 (1.01-1.28)	26.0	1.4	0.25
Childhood BMI (continuous)						
	Esophageal	3	1.51 (1.26-1.80)	0.0	0.07	0.96
	Liver	2	1.19 (1.07-1.33)	0.0	0.11	0.74
	Breast	2	1.42 (0.47-4.27)	78.9	4.74	0.03
	Colorectal	1	1.19 (1.06-1.33)	-	-	-
	Ovarian	1	2.20 (0.64-7.58)	-	-	-
	Lymphoma	1	1.09 (0.97-1.22)	-	-	-
	Multiple myeloma	1	1.15 (0.93-1.43)	-	-	-
	Leukemia	1	1.15 (0.95-1.39)	-	-	-
	Renal	1	1.03 (0.73-1.46)	-	-	-
Adolescent weight (continuous)						
	Breast	9	0.78 (0.71-0.87)	24.4	10.6	0.23
	Prostate	1	0.38 (0.17-0.86)	-	-	-
	Endometrial	2	1.25 (1.12-1.40)	0.0	0.6	0.43
Childhood weight (continuous)						
	Breast	12	0.70 (0.60-0.82)	68.9	35.4	<0.001
	Prostate	1	0.87 (0.67-1.13)	-	-	-
	Colorectal	2	1.41 (1.12-1.77)	2.4	1.0	0.31
	Endometrial	1	1.40 (1.16-1.69)	-	-	-
Childhood BMI and total physical activity (MET-h/wk _≥ 78)						
	Ovarian	2	1.04 (0.65-1.67)	0.0	0.1	0.75
Body Surface Area						
	Breast	3	0.97 (0.59-1.58)	0.0	0.43	0.81
Dairy consumption in childhood (no vs yes)						
	Testicular	1	0.53 (0.26-1.09)	-	-	-
Glucose (continuous)						
	All cancers	1	1.19 (1.08-1.31)	-	-	-
Prader-Willi syndrome						
	Leukemia	1	1.67 (0.72-3.28)	-	-	-
Systolic blood pressure (continuous)						
	All cancers	1	0.93 (0.76-1.13)	-	-	-
Total cholesterol (continuous)						
	All cancers	1	1.01 (0.83-1.23)	-	-	-
Triglycerides (continuous)						
	All cancers	1	0.93 (0.76-1.14)	-	-	-

*Statistical significant associations highlighted in bold; Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CI, confidence intervals; MET, metabolic equivalent; OR, odds ratio.

Breast cancer was the sole type of cancer where obesity was linked to a reduced risk. In particular, adolescent obesity was associated with reduced risk of breast cancer compared to normal-weight individuals, but this effect was not observed in childhood (Table 2). This finding was corroborated by a single study showing that the higher first incidence or older age of overweight status increased the risk for breast cancer, suggesting that the impact of obesity manifests later in life, during adolescence rather than childhood. To further explore this association, we also performed subgroup analyses for premenopausal and postmenopausal breast cancer (Table 3). Interestingly, adolescent obesity was statistically significantly associated with reduced risk of postmenopausal breast cancer, whereas the results for premenopausal breast cancer did not reach a level of statistical significance. Of note is that between-study heterogeneity was statistically significant in almost all meta-analyses for breast cancer. In addition, limited studies were available for sub-analyses, particularly for adolescents, and in one study, a positive association was reported between first incidence of overweight before puberty and breast cancer risk, but the 95% CIs of that study were rather broad (Table 3).

Table 3. Subgroup meta-analyses on the association between health-related indicators of childhood or adolescent obesity and adult breast cancer risk by pre- and postmenopausal status

Indices	Breast cancer all types				Premenopausal breast cancer				Postmenopausal breast cancer			
	N studies	Pooled OR* (95% CI)	I ²	p-value	N studies	Pooled OR* (95% CI)	I ²	p-value	N studies	Pooled OR* (95% CI)	I ²	p-value
Overweight in adolescence	11	0.92 (0.79-1.08)	50.3	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Obese in adolescence	9	0.73 (0.61-0.87)	58.5	0.01	1	2.90 (1.07-7.89)	-	-	1	0.80 (0.27-2.36)	-	-
Adolescent BMI (continuous)	2	0.95 (0.93-0.97)	0.0	0.99	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Childhood BMI (continuous)	8	0.88 (0.75-1.02)	48.1	0.06	2	0.71 (0.53-0.95)	68.6	0.07	2	0.57 (0.31-1.04)	92.2	<0.0001
Childhood weight (continuous)	9	0.89 (0.73-1.07)	82.9	<0.0001	6	0.85 (0.74-0.98)	62.7	0.02	3	0.72 (0.59-0.88)	0.0	0.52
Adolescent weight (continuous)	5	0.89 (0.83-0.95)	0.0	0.46	5	0.92 (0.82-1.02)	9.5	0.35	4	0.79 (0.69-0.91)	66.4	0.03
Body surface area	4	0.98 (0.69-1.39)	0.0	0.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
First incidence of overweight before puberty	1	2.70 (1.09-6.66)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
First incidence of overweight after puberty	1	1.90 (0.43-8.35)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*Statistical significant associations highlighted in bold; Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CI, confidence intervals; OR, odds ratio.

The present systematic review also identified other indicators as proxies of childhood obesity, such as body surface area, BMI in combination to total physical activity, dairy consumption, Prader-Willi syndrome, as well as glucose levels, systolic blood pressure, total cholesterol levels, and triglyceride levels (Table 2). A significant association was found for elevated glucose levels and increased risk for all cancers in adulthood (Table 2). For the remaining exposures, no associations were detected, but we should note that except for body surface area, only one study per exposure was available (Table 2).

1.4. Discussion

1.4.1. Comparison with previous studies

Our results align with previous systematic reviews and meta-analyses. Specifically, Llewellyn et al [16] reported that obesity in children aged 7-11 years was associated with increased risk of in adulthood, particularly of all cancers, hepatocellular carcinoma and liver cancer. Obese children aged above 12 years old also had increased risk for hepatocellular carcinoma, liver cancer, as well as colon, ovarian, renal and urothelial cancer in adult life. Importantly, this study reported that childhood obesity was not positively associated with breast cancer, though data about breast cancer was not included in that systematic review. Similarly, Mohammadian et al [17] reported that childhood obesity increased the risk for cancer incidence and mortality at later stage in life by 33% and by 28%, respectively. They found evidence that obesity increased the relative risk for prostate, renal cell and colorectal cancer and found a moderate negative association with breast cancer. In the pooled analysis for both genders, no association was found for hematologic cancers. Hidayat et al [18] reported a significant association between body fatness at young age (childhood, adolescence and early adulthood) and lymphoma, as well as colorectum, diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, endometrium, esophageal adenocarcinoma, gastric cardia, hepatocellular carcinoma, multiple myeloma, ovary, pancreas, renal cell and thyroid cancer. Interestingly, this study also found a reduced relative risk for both premenopausal and postmenopausal breast cancer. Ding et al [19] reported a positive association between childhood/adolescent obesity and ovarian cancer in both cohort and case-control studies, with the association being statistically significant at the age of 18 years and not at 10 years. The risk for cancer increased gradually with the degree of obesity. The meta-analysis by Garcia et al [20] suggested that high BMI levels increased by 39% the risk of colorectal cancer in adult men and by 19% in adult women.

1.4.2. Biological mechanisms

The main pathways that may underlie the association between childhood obesity and adult carcinogenesis are as follow:

- (1) *Insulin-like growth factors (IGFs)* synthesized by almost any tissue in the organism, that significantly contribute to cancer pathogenesis [21]. The IGF system is a sophisticated network that includes two growth factors (IGF-I and IGF-II), cell surface receptors (IGF-IR and IGF-IIR), proteases for IGF-binding proteins (IGFBP), six distinct high-affinity binding proteins (IGFBP-1 to IGFBP-6), and a plethora of IGFBP-interacting molecules. These components collectively orchestrate and drive IGF actions in a variety of tissues [21, 22]. The specific type of IGF-I receptor expressed by cancer cells could foster cell cycle progression and impede apoptosis, either directly or indirectly, by interacting with established oncogenic systems, such as steroid hormones and integrins [21].
- (2) *Sex hormones biosynthesis*. The process of steroid aromatization is regulated by the peripheral adipose tissue. The enzyme aromatase converts androgens and androgenic precursors to estradiol. In case of obesity excess adipose tissue, aromatase increased activity leads to higher conversion rates of androgens and androgenic precursors resulting in higher levels of estrogens [23]. Elevated levels of circulating sex hormones, such as dehydroepiandrosterone, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate, Δ^4 -androstenedione, testosterone, oestrone, and total estradiol, coupled with reduced concentrations of sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), have been linked to an increased risk of breast cancer in postmenopausal women [24, 25]. Testosterone has demonstrated a bimodal relationship with BMI, varying by gender.

Specifically, it tends to be elevated in obese women while being reduced in obese men. High serum concentrations of androgens have been linked to an increased breast cancer risk in women, irrespective of their menopausal status [24, 25]. However, the impact of testosterone on mammary tissue remains unclear based on current basic research [23]. Obesity is associated with a 2.6-fold increased risk of endometrial cancer (EC) compared to normal weight [26]. Estrogen is known to promote tumorigenesis in endometrial tissue by stimulating cell proliferation and inhibiting apoptosis. These effects are mediated by the induction of IGF1 production in endometrial tissue, which then acts on the endometrium in a paracrine manner [26]. Conversely, progesterone counteracts estrogen effects primarily by stimulating the production of IGF1 binding protein, which subsequently inhibits IGF1 [27]. IGF2 mediates the effects of progesterone during the luteinizing phase of the menstrual cycle and plays a crucial role in endometrial differentiation and interactions with the fetus. The primary sex-hormone hypothesis for EC is the unopposed estrogen effect. Ovarian hyperandrogenism is another proposed mechanism linking obesity, sex-hormone dysregulation, and EC [27].

- (3) *Subclinical chronic low-grade inflammation and oxidative DNA damage.* Obesity is associated with chronic inflammation which can mediate cancer development and progression as many inflammatory components reside in the tumor microenvironment and promote a cancerous phenotype [28, 29]. Adipose tissue, functioning as an active endocrine organ, secretes various adipocytokines into the bloodstream, with adiponectin and leptin being the most significant [30]. Adiponectin, a hormone produced by adipose tissue, exhibits anti-inflammatory and insulin-sensitizing properties [31]. Adiponectin levels inversely correlate with inflammatory cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin (IL)-6, which are elevated in obesity, and can also attenuate nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) activation [32]. Leptin levels, on the other hand, positively correlate with BMI and adipose tissue mass. Unlike adiponectin, leptin has pro-inflammatory effects, stimulating the production of IL-1, IL-6, IL-12, TNF- α , Leukotriene B4 (LTB-4), and Cyclooxygenase 2 (COX2). Additionally, it promotes T cell proliferation and TH1 phenotype while suppressing Regulatory T (Treg) cells [33]. Hypoadiponectinemia has been observed in numerous malignancies, underscoring its tumor-suppressive role. However, epidemiological data regarding leptin levels in relation to cancer have been inconsistent, despite many experimental studies using supraphysiological levels of leptin [34-38]. Obesity is causally related to insulin resistance (IR), which may potentially promote inflammation [39]. Inflammatory adipocytokines, apart from their direct effect on tissues, influence the sex hormone mechanism of tumorigenesis via stimulation of estrogen production by aromatase. A recent study clarified the effect of systemic inflammation on overall and cancer-related mortality [40]. Increased mortality rates were observed in individuals with elevated Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) and/or high sensitivity C-reactive protein (hsCRP) levels [40]. Interestingly, the effect of systemic inflammation on cancer-related mortality was found to be more pronounced. Tumor progression in obesity-related malignancies involves IR, inflammation, and tumor infiltration with immune cells [41].
- (4) *Alterations in adipocytokine pathophysiology.* Obesity chronic inflammatory state triggers alterations of normal leptin and adiponectin levels, which in combination with the co-occurrence of other changes, including infiltration of macrophages, mitochondrial dysfunction and increased endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress response, may be associated with promotion of cancers such as CRC in obese individuals [42]. Ectopic adipose tissue may pose a more significant risk factor for site-specific cancers. Findings from the Framingham Heart Study suggest that the risk for malignancies could be higher for metabolically unhealthy obese

(MUO) older individuals compared to metabolically healthy obese (MHO) adults [43]. Emerging evidence from epidemiological and translational research studies suggests that local ectopic fat tissue, such as that found in the breast, bone marrow, liver, and pancreas, may exert toxic and carcinogenic effects, contributing to the development of breast, hematopoietic, liver, and pancreatic cancers [44, 45]. Adiponectin, the most prevalent adipokine in the bloodstream, is the initial hormone to become dysregulated (resulting in hypoadiponectinemia) due to intra-abdominal and ectopic fat distribution. This dysregulation subsequently leads to disturbances in Insulin-like Growth Factors (IGFs), inflammation, estrogen/progesterone imbalance, culminating in neoplastic transformation [46].

- (5) *Microenvironment & cellular perturbations mechanisms.* Vascular perturbations provide a low-grade inflammation mechanism associated with “angiogenic switch” that contributes to carcinogenesis [47]; Epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) changes can reduce cell adhesion to other cells and matrix, increasing cell motility [48]; Endoplasmic Reticulum (ER) Stress is involved in protein folding and obesity is associated with ER stress in adipocytes. Migrating Adipose Progenitor Cells: the stroma of tumors contains mesenchymal cells (MSCs) that serve as important progenitor cells which, in turn, play an important role in carcinogenesis [49].

1.4.3. Strengths and limitations

A major strength of the present systematic review was the extensive literature search of approximately 16,500 publications using different sources. Our analysis was based on 59 publications providing a substantial number of studies for a systematic review. We examined the association of childhood obesity with 22 different types of cancer, thus covering a broad range of cancer phenotypes. We also explored the association of obesity with cancer at different stages of childhood and adolescence, as well as the potential effect of obesity on pre- and postmenopausal breast cancer. To our knowledge, this is the only systematic review that included 22 different types of cancer and various definitions for childhood obesity.

Limitations of our systematic review primarily include issues of heterogeneity and potential bias. There was considerable variation in the definition of exposure across different populations thus leading to significant between-study heterogeneity. The potential effect of childhood obesity was evaluated on various types of cancer, but due to the limited number of studies for certain subtypes, there was again significant between-study heterogeneity. Lastly, our review included a variety of study designs, such as cohort studies, case-control studies, nested case-control studies, and cross-sectional studies, which may also have contributed to significant heterogeneity.

2. Survey of Current Intervention Policies and Gap/Obstacles Identification

Data on current intervention policies and weight control strategies targeting children and adolescents were collected from Greece, Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden, in these three countries the pilot PREVENT interventions will be implemented. Interventions, policies and strategies were described in detail and were grouped in different scales/context in which they were implemented, such as school, family, community, clinical setting and the whole society context. The main barriers and gaps for the implementation of each intervention/policy in terms of cost, social and cultural constraints and acceptability were identified and organized in different domains, ranging from the individual, family and peers to the whole society and public policy domain.

Furthermore, WP2 PREVENT partners were also requested to provide their feedback, from their area of expertise, concerning the main barriers and gaps related to existing interventions/policies/strategies to prevent childhood obesity implemented worldwide and not explicitly focusing on specific interventions/policies/strategies found in the pilot countries.

The results of the survey will provide useful input for formulating the proposed PREVENT interventions based on a multi-actor and context aware primary prevention approach, along with specific engagement policies and educational plans, with the aim of addressing the identified barriers.

2.1. Methodology

The survey was conducted via a combination of consultations with the members of the Communities of Practice (CoP) in the three demo countries and an online survey distributed to CoP members and PREVENT partners.

The consultation with the CoP members was performed in the three demo countries over physical and online meetings during which the CoP members were asked to report current primary interventions/policies/strategies addressing childhood obesity in their countries and discuss their relevance with the proposed PREVENT approach.

The content of the survey was originally developed by the National Public Health Organization (NPHO) of Greece and reviewed by the WP2 partners in the other two demo countries, namely Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden. The purpose of the survey was to gather information on the current interventions, policies and strategies that are implemented in the three demo countries in relation to the primary prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence, and specifically targeting children and adolescents between 9-16 years old. An additional primary aim of the survey was to identify the barriers or obstacles that have been observed during the implementation of each of the intervention/policy /strategy identified, with the final goal to explore ways to overcome them.

The survey included a total of 44 questions with both closed and open-ended questions. The questions collected information on the type and content of the intervention/policy/strategy, the health-related outcomes of interest, the scale/context of implementation, the level and setting of the implementation, the target population and stakeholders involved, the place and duration of implementation, the type of materials and/or tools used for the implementation, especially digital ones, the existence of a legal framework to support the intervention, the existence of enforcement methods and funding sources, and the monitoring scheme, if any. There were also questions on the use of behavioral models in which the interventions were based and the use of participatory methods.

For the identification of barriers, respondents were asked to categorize any identified barrier to specific categories: cost/financing barriers, social/cultural barriers, acceptability barriers and other implementation barriers. All barriers were matched to a specific implementation domain ranging from the individual, family and peers, childcare and school, community and built environment, society, to public policy (see also Appendix 1).

Lastly, there was a question on the identification of opportunities and/or actions that will help to overcome the identified barriers and facilitate the successful implementation of the interventions. The questionnaire used for the survey can be found in Appendix 2.

A second shorter survey focusing only on the identification of barriers and opportunities was also distributed to all WP2 PREVENT partners in order to provide their feedback from their area of expertise. The purpose of this second survey was to have a general overview of the main barriers and gaps regarding existing policies/strategies worldwide. The short survey questionnaire can be found in Appendix 3.

Both surveys did not collect personal data and were distributed via an anonymous online survey. The online survey was built with the support of the Institute of Communication & Computer Systems (ICCS) and it was distributed separately in the three demo countries.

2.2. Results - Summary characteristics of interventions/policies/strategies from the demo countries

The WP2 partners in each of the demo countries compiled a country-specific report with the results of the survey conducted in their country. A summary of the data collected grouped by their main characteristics is described below. The full country-specific reports can be found in Appendices 4 (for Greece), 5 (for Spain, Catalonia) and 6 (for Sweden).

A total of 6, 7 and 3 interventions/policies/strategies were identified to be most relevant to proceed to the next phase of PREVENT in Greece, Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden, respectively. Of note that Sweden, provided 3 reports related to: a) The school meal system, b) The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme and c) Food advertising. For the latter, six (6) laws/policies/acts related to food advertising were identified.

2.2.1. Type and content

Greece

Out of the selected six intervention/policies/strategies in Greece, three (50%) were policies /strategies (**the National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents, the School Canteen Standards, WHO Child Growth Standards**) and three (50%) were interventions (**Health Promotion Education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education, the EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme, the Public information campaign on healthy nutrition**).

The **National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents'** guidelines form a national **policy**. The guidelines constitute an essential nutrition policy tool used to inform and educate the general population about healthy dietary habits and regular physical activity for infants, children and adolescents with the ultimate goal to protect and promote their health. The guidelines are evidence-based and are provided in the form of frequency and amount of consumption of main food

groups. Healthy tips for meal consumption, preparation and preservation and behavioral advice to establish and promote healthy dietary habits and behaviors in children and adolescents are also provided.

The **School Canteens Standards** (with an official catalogue of food-products approved for sale at the Greek school canteens) are mandatory for all school canteens in private and public schools in Greece. They are considered a **policy**. The Standards were developed in 2013 by the National Nutrition Policy Committee based in previous standards and were adopted from the Greek Ministry of Health. Their main objective is to promote healthy eating and healthy food choices during school hours, as well as protect student's health from the regular consumption of food-products considered unhealthy.

The **WHO Child Growth Standards** were endorsed as national growth standards in 2017 substituting previous national growth standards. They are considered a **policy**. The standards are used for recording and monitoring physical growth and development of Greek infants, children and adolescents and they are embedded in the Personal Child Record of each child born in Greece. The main objective of the growth standards is to determine whether a child is growing "normally" or has a growth problem, or trend towards a growth problem, that should be addressed.

The **Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education** can be considered an **intervention** program. It involves educational material that was developed and launched in 2019 by the Hellenic Dietetics Association with the aim to educate children and raise their awareness in relation to the importance of healthy and balanced dietary habits. The material was approved by the Ministry of Health and the Institute of Educational Policy of the Ministry of Education. The material is available for the teachers to be used as part of the Health Education in schools. The implementation of the education is optional and depends on the teacher that will be responsible for its implementation. The main objective is to educate children and raise their awareness of the importance of healthy and balanced dietary habits.

The **EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme** is an EU project which supports the distribution of milk, fruit and vegetables to millions of children, from nursery to secondary school, across the EU as part of a wider programme of education about European agriculture and the benefits of healthy eating. The Scheme, which can be characterized as an **intervention program**, was launched in Greece during 2009-2010 school year and merged with the EU School Milk Scheme on 1 August 2017 into one legal framework based on the Regulation on the new School Fruit, Vegetables and Milk Scheme (Regulation EU No 2016/791). It supports the distribution of products, educational measures and information measures with the aim of promoting healthy eating habits, to educate about agriculture and food production, and to enhance overall well-being.

The **Public information campaign on healthy nutrition** and dietary habits is being implemented periodically on a national level in order to increase awareness of the general population on healthy nutrition habits and other relevant issues. This campaign is considered one of the actions implemented in the context of Greek national nutrition policy and it can be considered an **intervention** action.

Spain (Catalonia)

In Spain, Catalonia the most relevant interventions identified as to the most appropriate to proceed to the next phase of PREVENT were seven interventions (the **Daily Mile**, **Active Pauses**, the **School Menus**

Review Programme: More Healthy and Sustainable School Canteens-PreME-MEMSS, Prevention and management of childhood obesity in the neighbourhood La Mina-La Mina, INFADIMED, Science Engagement to Empower Disadvantaged Adolescents-SEEDS and SEISMO).

The selected interventions are related to promotion of children's and adolescents' healthy eating and physical activity in school and community environments considering social determinants.

The **Daily Mile** is an **intervention** focused on promoting social **physical activity** that takes place outside during the school day at a time of the teacher's choosing, with the objective of improving physical, social, emotional and mental health and wellbeing of the children – regardless of age, ability or personal circumstances.

The **Active Pauses** is an **intervention** characterized by short periods of **physical activity**, which last between 5 and 10 minutes and take place within the classroom. The activity aims to reduce the time of inactivity of students during school hours, develop a positive attitude toward physical activity and increase daily energy expenditure in physical activity. To facilitate its implementation, the intervention is designed to work on curricular content, in a limited space like the classroom, and can be done any time during the day.

The **School Menus Review Programme: More Healthy and Sustainable School Canteens (PreME-MEMSS)** is an **intervention** that evaluates the **menus of pre-school**, primary and secondary schools that have a canteen service, and promotes changes in their menu planning to promote **healthier and more sustainable food**. It also aims to know the acceptance of the meals served in order to increase their nutritional quality and initiate strategies that lead to reduce food waste; therefore, it aims to care for the health of people, territories and the planet at the same time. It has different phases including evaluation, training, action plan on necessary improvements, implementation of changes, and final evaluation and continuation.

The **La Mina** is a **primary health care centre** and **community-based intervention** on prevention and management of childhood obesity in the neighbourhood La Mina, which is a vulnerable high-priority neighbourhood. The model of prevention and care for childhood obesity is based on a multidisciplinary and multilevel approach to the individual aspects and the environment of the child and the family, with the aim of acting on: nutrition, physical activity and exercise, sedentary lifestyle and screen time, leisure, hours of sleep and positive and respectful parenting, considering social determinants.

The **INFADIMED** is a primary health care **intervention** on the promotion of the Mediterranean diet as a healthy lifestyle for students aged 3 to 12 with interventions in **schools and the community**. Nurses trained in the intervention provide healthy lifestyle education at schools and community centers with interactive education materials including a series of cartoons. It is currently piloting a streaming platform to bring content to families via mobile devices.

The **Science Engagement to Empower Disadvantaged Adolescents (SEEDS)** is an **intervention** funded by the European Union. The intervention is based on extreme citizen science, and adolescents from Greece, UK, the Netherlands and Spain with leadership characteristics are named ambassadors and co-create interventions for the improvement of lifestyles, focusing on physical activity and snacking behavior while increasing STEM interest of their peers.

The **SEISMO** is a randomized controlled trial of a **School-based health Education Intervention to Stimulate the resilience and Motivation for preventing paediatric Obesity** among vulnerable populations. The project seeks to make the subject of Physical Education the epicenter of a healthy earthquake which expands into tutorships and all educational spaces in the school by involving the entire educational community, providing teachers with tools and materials to integrate healthy habits in the school. The main objective is to encourage the physical, psychological, and social development of children aged 6–12 through the promotion of **healthy habits and abilities for life**, bringing about distinct acts in the school environment and implying all levels of the educational community—the students, their families and teachers.

Sweden

In Sweden, one (33%) of the three selected interventions is related to regulations and it is a mixture of laws, policies, interventions, and strategies on food advertising, one (33%) is a law, and one (33%) is an intervention that operates within a policy framework (**The regulations related to exposure to food advertising and its association with dietary behaviors, The school meal system and The European school fruit vegetables and milk scheme**).

The **regulations related to exposure to food advertising and its association with dietary behaviors** are laws, policies, interventions, and strategies on advertising, marketing, communications, internet, and use of digital means.

The **school meal system** is a law on the provision of free school nutritious meals in primary schools, with the potential for expansion in older age groups. This provision is under the Education Act, which dictates that all primary school pupils (ages 6-15) are legally entitled to education, including materials and nutritious school meals, free of charge. In relation to the school meals, the Swedish Food Agency, has issued non-binding guidelines that state that meals are expected to meet nutritional recommendations over a four-week period and include general information about foods to promote.

The **European school fruit vegetables and milk scheme** is an EU-wide intervention that operates within a policy framework and provides funding and support for the distribution of milk, fruits, and vegetables in educational institutions across EU member states. Its primary goal is to encourage nutritious dietary choices and raise awareness about agriculture and food production processes.

2.2.2. Health outcome targeted

Greece

In Greece, for the majority (5/6, 83%) of the six selected interventions/policies/strategies, there is no specific health outcome targeted but the overall optimal health, development, and well-being, prevention of nutritional deficiencies, maintenance of normal weight and prevention of obesity and chronic diseases later in life.

The outcomes of the *WHO Child Growth Standards* are the indices who reflect growth and development. Specific anthropometric indices are measured such as body weight, body length or height, head circumference and body mass index.

Spain (Catalonia)

Like Greece, the majority (4/7, 57%) of the seven selected interventions/policies/strategies in Catalonia, Spain target more general health outcomes such as the overall optimal growth and development, improvement of the children's fitness levels (and consequently their bone health, muscle strength, and heart health, and reduction of body fat and promotions of healthy body composition), social, physical and emotional well-being, and academic performance.

Anthropometric indices, such as BMI z-score and waist-to-height ratio, are measured as outcomes (in addition to others) in 3 out of the 7 selected interventions (La Mina, INFADIMED, SEISMO).

The SEISMO study also has incidence of overweight, obesity, severe obesity and abdominal obesity as health outcomes.

Other health outcomes targeted include level of life satisfaction (La Mina), snacking behavior and STEM outcomes (interest in life science, science capital, and interest in STEM career pathways) (SEEDS) and quality of life outcomes.

Sweden

Similar to most interventions/policies/strategies in Greece and Spain, all three (3/3, 100%) selected policies/interventions do not have a specific health outcome targeted. On the other hand, they indirectly influence positively children's health and well-being, promote education and academic performance and help children make healthier choices. Of course, indirectly contribute to efforts in reducing overweight and obesity.

2.2.3. Scale/context, Level and Sector of implementation

Greece

Five of the six (5/6, 83%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are implemented in schools while other settings that are relevant for certain interventions/policies/strategies are child-care settings, families, communities, clinical and other health settings, mass media, municipal markets, sports facilities, as well as in the whole society.

In terms of level of implementation, all six interventions/policies are implemented at national level.

Regarding the sector of implementation, the vast majority (5/6, 83%) of the policies/interventions are implemented in both the public and private sector.

Spain (Catalonia)

All seven (7/7, 100%) selected interventions/policies/strategies in Spain are implemented in schools while other settings that are relevant for certain interventions/policies/strategies are families, primary health care centres, municipal markets, the community, with a broader scope of the whole society as well as public policy.

In terms of level of implementation, the selected interventions/policies/strategies are implemented at different levels including national, regional, and local.

Regarding the sector of implementation, 5 out of 7 of the policies/interventions (71%) are implemented in both the public and private sector.

Sweden

Two of the three (2/3, 67%) selected interventions/policies/strategies in Sweden are implemented in schools while the third that is related to different regulations on exposure to food advertising and its

association with dietary behaviors are implemented in the whole society as the regulations deal with broadcasting and media regulation, marketing practices, order-based TV, and video sharing platforms, digital services, safer internet, advertising and communications and audiovisual media policies.

In terms of the level of implementation, the three selected interventions, policies, and strategies are implemented at a national level. However, the school meal system, specifically for high schools (pupils older than 15 years of age), is implemented at the local level as local authorities/municipalities run schools. Additionally, the EU School Fruit, Vegetables, and Milk Scheme is partially implemented (only the milk portion) in Sweden at a national level.

Regarding the sector of implementation, all (3/3, 100%) of the policies/interventions/strategies are implemented in both the public and private sector.

2.2.4. Target populations and target stakeholders

Greece

All six (6/6, 100%) selected interventions/policies/strategies target children and adolescents with most of them (4/6, 67%) targeting individuals up to 18 years old. Other target populations include parents, teachers and headteachers as well as the whole population.

In terms of stakeholders, in all six interventions/policies/strategies there is a variety of stakeholder groups involved including policy makers and other governmental authorities, parents and caregivers, health professionals, nutritionists, people responsible for the school canteens and schools' meals, school principals, teachers and professors, the food industry, business related to marketing of food products to children.

Spain (Catalonia)

All seven (7/7, 100%) selected interventions/policies/strategies target children and adolescents up to 16 years old. Families are also included in the target population of certain interventions/policies/strategies.

In terms of stakeholders, there is a variety of stakeholder groups involved in the seven selected interventions/policies/strategies such as educational entities including the school administration and teaching personnel, public health agencies, health care services, municipalities, government agencies, business and academia, other entities working with children (playgrounds, play centers, libraries, civic centers, sports clubs/associations, etc.), City Hall, food suppliers/stores, associated entities, etc.

Sweden

All (3/3, 100%) three selected interventions/policies/strategies target children and adolescents up to 16 years old. Other target populations include parents and guardians, professionals working with children, all citizens including viewers, listeners, consumers and businesses, users of digital services, companies and organizations that use or provide audio-visual or media services.

In terms of stakeholders, there is a variety of stakeholder groups involved in the three selected interventions/policies/strategies such as children, adolescents, parents and guardians, educational institutions including teachers and school health care staff, local authorities, local authority catering staff, companies and foundations that run private schools, national authorities and agencies, farmers, and producers, EU institutions, media literacy educators, consumers, businesses, industry associations, legal professionals, digital service providers, goods and services providers, smaller platforms and start-

ups, civil society organizations and advocacy groups, tech industry associations and trade groups, academics and researchers, advertisers, marketing practitioners, regulators, self-regulatory bodies, emerging mediums, media companies, cultural and creative sectors, technology companies, environmental groups, public and citizens.

2.2.5. Place and duration of the implementation

Greece

The majority of the six (5/6, 83%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are implemented throughout the country.

All six of them (6/6, 100%) are currently in effect ranging from 6 to 13 years since initiation.

Spain (Catalonia)

Five of the seven (5/7, 71%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are or will be implemented in Catalonia, among which one in a neighbourhood in the city of Barcelona. Another one is implemented in primary schools throughout Spain and one in high schools from deprived areas across Spain.

In terms of duration, five of the seven (5/7, 71%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are currently being implemented ranging from 2 to 6 years since initiation. One intervention was implemented in the past and one is currently undergoing the process of review and authorisation.

Sweden

All three (3/3, 100%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are implemented throughout Sweden. In terms of duration, all three (3/3, 100%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are currently in effect with two of them ranging from 2 to 26 years of duration since initiation while some of the regulations included on the food advertisement regulations date back to 1937.

2.2.6. Material and tools

Greece

In the majority (5/6, 83%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies, printed material is being used in the form of posters, pamphlets, brochures, guides, guidelines, and publications to general newspapers. In most of the cases, the material is also available in an electronic format with online access for certain populations groups such as parents, guardians, caregivers, teachers, older children, and health professionals.

Two interventions (the EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme & Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education) use digital tools such as power-point presentations, an online platform with specific thematic sections, a teacher's guide, and multimodal/interactive educational material. Other materials used include products (fruits, vegetables, and milk), course presentations, unit consolidation/assessment activities, and games.

Spain (Catalonia)

The majority of the (4/7, 57%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies incorporates digital tools. Examples are webinars, online applications for entering school menu information and extracting evaluation reports based on recommended criteria, online platforms, toolbox for promoting healthy

lifestyles and/or monitoring physical activity with the inclusion of eating challenges, infographics, diary for monitoring commitments or challenge calendars, self-monitoring, workshops. In addition, emails, online meetings, WhatsApp/cell phones, and animated cartoons with interactive print materials are also tools used in the context of the selected interventions/policies/strategies.

Other tools used in certain interventions/policies/strategies include newsletters, review sheets, tables of recommended frequencies of food, Individual school reports, questionnaires, informative materials, guides and recommendations, food recipes, behavioural support workshops, educational material. Activity modules are also incorporated and include physical education (utilizing sports activities, collages, the Harvard health eating plate, implementation support resources, etc.) family (utilizing home activities, children tutoring, motivational messages, video tips about healthy habits for families, etc.) and healthy spaces modules that promote the improvement and transformation of recreational spaces.

Sweden

Two of the three (67%) selected interventions/policies/strategies do not rely on digital tools as a central feature while the third (on food advertisement regulations) involves a diverse array of materials and methods.

Materials and tools used include fresh produce distribution, educational activities, information measures to promote healthy eating habits among schoolchildren. In addition, for the implementation of the selected intervention/policy on different regulations are legislative text, public consultations, stakeholder dialogues, research and evidence, collaboration with industry, guidance documents, impact assessments, and legislative acts, webinars for professionals and schools, educational resources, media literacy training tools, cross-sector collaboration, mobile supplements, frameworks, EU programs, regulatory frameworks, cooperation, and dialogue.

Examples of digital tools utilized for the implementation of certain regulations are helplines, hotlines, youth panels, and platforms to enhance online safety for children and young people, free online courses on ethical marketing, updated implementation guides, digital platforms, interactive tools, media data spaces, virtual and augmented reality tools as well as EU supported innovative tools. Emerging digital marketing and advertising practices such as AI-enabled marketing, market influencers, vloggers, and data analytics are also considered within a regulation.

2.2.7. Application of behavioral models and co-creation/participatory methods

Greece

None of the six selected interventions/policies/strategies have applied a behavioral model or utilized co-creation/participatory methods. However, in some cases of the selected interventions/policies/strategies even if they do not explicitly use co-creation participatory methods as primary approach, they involve collaboration among various stakeholders, who collectively contribute to the successful implementation of the program.

Spain (Catalonia)

Two (2/7, 29%) of the seven selected interventions/policies/strategies did not apply a behavioral model or utilized co-creation/participatory methods.

Three (3/7, 43%) selected interventions/policies/strategies applied/apply a behavioral model such as the Transtheoretical model, Motivational interviewing, Positive parenting, the ASE Model, as well as the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Resilience theory.

Five (5/7, 71%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies utilized co-creation/participatory methods, such as systematically receiving feedback from involved parties, review of school menus accompanied by the provision of suggestions of improvement and follow-up of the actions taken. Assessment of school meals and the agents involved (school management, management company, canteen monitors, families) and incorporation of requests and suggestions is also employed. In addition, group sessions with community leaders/stakeholders, health care professionals' training seminars on positive parenting and attention to vulnerable families and the motivational interview, information sessions for professionals and neighbourhood entities, satisfaction surveys for professionals, children and families and focus groups with children are some other participatory methods used in an intervention. In another intervention, the involved parties reflect on the subjects worked on, the content is reviewed and new health issues of concern to the teaching and health community are proposed leading to the adaptation of the educational content to the new needs. Activities in the community are also agreed with the promoters within the community. In an intervention that uses the Citizen Science approach, focus groups along with online tutorials and exercises prepare the target population for Makeathons.

Sweden

None of the three selected interventions/policies/strategies have applied a behavioral model while in one of the three (33%), co-creation participatory methods are considered essential for their implementation.

The regulations related to exposure to food advertising and its association with dietary behaviors employ co-creation participatory methods to shape policies and regulations across various sectors. These methods involve collaboration and engagement with diverse stakeholders through dialogues, policy exchanges and cooperation across member states etc.

However, even if the other two selected interventions/policies/strategies do not explicitly use co-creation participatory methods as primary approach, they both involve collaboration among various stakeholders, who collectively contribute to the successful implementation of the program. In some cases, council discussions with the participation of the involved stakeholders take place.

2.2.8. Legal framework support, enforcement methods, funding

Greece

The majority (4/6, 67%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies are supported by either a national or European legal framework while two (2/6, 33%) of them are enforced by certain methodology such as through regular monitoring and application of fines if deviations are detected. In terms of funding, four (4/6, 67%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies were/are funded by public funding and/or EU funds while for two (2/6, 33%), no funds are needed.

Spain (Catalonia)

Three (3/7, 43%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies are supported by a legal framework while two (2/7, 29%) of them are enforced. In terms of funding, four (4/7, 57%) of the interventions/policies/strategies are publicly funded with two of them also receiving some private funds. Two (2/7, 29%) of the rest do not require any funds.

Sweden

All three (3/3, 100%) selected interventions/policies/strategies are supported either a national or European legal framework while for two (2/3, 67%) of them enforcement is considered a collaborative effort between stakeholders such as EU institutions, national authorities, schools, and various stakeholders. The third one on various regulations, certain national or EU authorities or a combination of them are responsible for the enforcement of each regulation. In terms of funding, one is publicly funded, one is EU-funded and the third one on regulations receives funding from national public, EU or private sources or a combination of them depending on the regulation.

2.2.9. Monitoring

Greece

For the majority (5/6, 83%) of the selected interventions/policies/strategies, there is no monitoring mechanism in place. Only one intervention, that is an EU program, is being monitored by national authorities using both process and outcome indicators.

Spain (Catalonia)

All (7/7 100%) the selected interventions/policies/strategies are being monitored by either schools, public health agencies, health, school and community services, or researchers. The indicators used for monitoring were reported for only one intervention, and they were related to process and outcomes.

Sweden

For two (2/3, 67%) of the three selected interventions/policies/strategies, monitoring is in place by either national or EU authorities, organizations, including NGOs. For the third intervention/policy/strategy there is a web-based self-monitoring tool available for those who choose to use it. The indicators used are both process and outcome indicators and can be a mix of quantitative and qualitative indicators. Compliance is also often being monitored.

2.2.10. Barriers

The identified barriers/obstacles to the implementation of the selected interventions/policies/strategies of each country in the three nodes are summarized in **Table 4** (see Appendix 1).

The barriers are categorized in three main groups, as requested by the survey, namely barriers related to: a) cost/financing constraints, b) social/cultural constraints and c) degree of the acceptability of the intervention/policy/strategy.

In addition, survey respondents were asked to identify other implementation barriers not included in the above categories, if any, considering domains that could be related to the individual, the family & peers, the childcare facilities & school, the community & built environment, the society, and the public

policy (as shown in the Table included in the survey questionnaire, see Appendix 1/Table 6 & Appendix 2).

All barriers reported are presented in **Table 5** (see Appendix 1) classified by the above-mentioned domains.

2.2.11. Areas of opportunities/ Opportunities for improvement

Greece

In Greece, several areas and opportunities for improvement were reported for the selected intervention/policies/strategies including increasing the use of digital tools, the establishment of monitoring mechanisms, the use of co-creation participatory methods while a prominent opportunity for improvement was wider dissemination to target populations. In addition, funding and improvement of the logistical procedures were also reported.

Spain (Catalonia)

Similarly, to Greece, Spain survey results indicated wider dissemination using different means (e.g., online platforms, promotion through ambassadors) and increased funds were also frequently reported as areas for improvement. Education, training and raising awareness among all involved parties as well as the use of digital tools and co-creation participatory methods with an equity perspective were also reported. Improvement of logistical procedures such as the access to school premises, curriculum changes and built environment improvements could help overcome barriers to the implementation of certain interventions and policies, while regulations including prohibitions on unhealthy food advertising targeted at children and adolescents will facilitate the implementation of primary prevention of obesity interventions. Good examples such as self-sustainable activities (e.g. physical activity groups), and a comprehensive and personalized approach compared to the usual advice and treatment for childhood obesity (as part of primary health care intervention) can be replicated in other relevant interventions.

Sweden

Increased use of digital tools for the implementation and monitoring of interventions as well as continuous education, regular updates, collaboration, and promotion of the benefits of certain interventions and policies were proposed by the survey results of the Swedish node. Special attention was given on the digital food advertisements targeted at children and young audiences with a call for a comprehensive analysis of the exposure as well as the influence that food content, as well as food advertisement, have in children and teenagers as a public health initiative, that could foster significant outcomes and may inform and shape current policies.

With respect to the European school fruit vegetables and milk scheme, areas of opportunity for improvement are: a) the design and implementation of a technology-based system for the onsite distribution of fruits (mainly) and vegetables in Swedish schools, b) focus on automated monitoring of fruit/vegetable distribution to the end users and association with real-world dietary habit changes, c) identification and test the pragmatic school and student needs with regards to preferred deployment parameters at the school and student's awareness raising for health-benefits, short and long-term.

For the School Meal System in Sweden, the demonstration of the effect of issuing vouchers on school lunch quality, as well as investigation whether lunch quality is affected by the food establishments and advertising in the local environment surrounding upper secondary schools, is proposed.

2.3. Results of the short survey on barriers among PREVENT partners

A total of six answers were received on the second shorter survey that was focused only on the identification of barriers and opportunities related to interventions/policies/ strategies and distributed to all PREVENT partners in order for them to provide their feedback from their area of expertise. As described in the Methodology section, the purpose of this second survey was to have an overview of the main barriers and gaps regarding existing policies worldwide and regardless of a specific intervention/policy/strategy (see survey short questionnaire in Appendix 3).

The results of the short survey are presented below in the following four categories: a) cost/financing constraints, b) social/cultural constraints, c) degree of acceptability and d) other implementation barriers.

2.3.1. Cost/Financing Constraints

For EU Projects, obesity is recognized as Non-Communicable Disease and needs to be framed as a chronic, relapsing disease. Regarding the cost/financing constraints related to obesity, implementation costs vary based on national funding. At EU level, complex processes around funding/budget for specific public health strategies is a barrier. Bureaucratic procedures may delay/complicate funding allocation for new/developing interventions. Also, costs of interventions pose barriers to successful implementation with associated personnel, resource, and equipment costs. Most interventions require direct financial investment to provide resources/infrastructure. Furthermore, technological platforms/equipment used to enhance these interventions undoubtedly add to overall implementation cost. Another barrier related to indirect costs include competing time commitments for educators/curriculum developers.

Moreover, governments at various levels may face competing priorities for allocating limited budgets. Funding for obesity prevention programs may be insufficient compared to other pressing public health concerns, leading to challenges in implementing comprehensive interventions. Additionally, within government agencies, resources may be allocated unevenly, with a greater emphasis on treating rather than preventing obesity, as well as with no consistency across regions of the same country. The short-term funding cycles and budget uncertainties can undermine the sustainability of obesity prevention initiatives. Without stable funding streams, programs may struggle to maintain momentum and achieve long-term impacts.

Another significant cost/funding barrier concerns school environment. Participating in prevention programs may require time investments by schools, children, and their families, potentially leading to challenges for working parents, but also displacement of time spent on other school subjects mandated in the curriculum. Schools may face budget constraints that limit their ability to implement obesity prevention strategies effectively. Also, costs around transportation to program locations or special equipment to support interventions can create barriers for schools/families with limited resources. Moreover, there is the infrastructure costs in schools. Creating environments conducive to

healthy eating and physical activity in schools often requires infrastructure investments, such as building playgrounds, upgrading cafeteria facilities, and implementing wellness policies.

Additional considerations for cost include sustainability and equity. Securing long-term funding for prevention programs is crucial for sustained impact. Reliance on short-term grants or funding initiatives can create uncertainty and hinder long-term program effectiveness. Frequent changes in funding availability or short-term grants can make it difficult to implement and sustain long-term prevention programs.

Lastly, cost-related barriers can be particularly challenging in underserved areas, such as low-income families and communities, limiting their access to effective prevention programs, and exacerbating existing health disparities. The above has as consequence the inability of funding sustainably interventions, e.g. offering meals at schools, reimbursing the purchase of specific products per age group, or hold nutrition education programs for families. Moreover, low-income families face the inability to purchase and provide high quality/nutritious foods to their members. Families with lower socioeconomic status may have to deal with barriers such as limited access to healthy foods, safe outdoor spaces for physical activity, and healthcare services. Economic constraints can also make healthier options less affordable.

2.3.2. Social/Cultural Constraints

Social and cultural factors can significantly influence attitudes and behaviors related to health interventions, creating barriers to effective delivery. In terms of cultural influences, body image, food traditions and practices and expectations around health behaviors may pose barriers to intervention success and may differ across Europe depending on population/country. Varying cultural perceptions of ideal body size can deter individuals from seeking support or engaging in interventions. Cultural food habits and preferences might prioritize specific dietary patterns that may not align with nutritional recommendations for children/adolescents. Different cultures may have social norms regarding physical activity participation, especially for girls or adolescents, potentially hindering their engagement in physical activity programs.

Family plays a crucial role in shaping children's dietary habits and physical activity levels. Parental knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding healthy eating and physical activity directly impact children's habits. Additionally, family structures and cultural expectations around child-rearing practices may influence physical activity levels and dietary choices. Cultural traditions, beliefs, and practices within the family environment can either support or hinder efforts to prevent obesity. For instance, in some cultures still being fat is a sign of prosperity, but of course this is more common among low educated people. In some cases, cultural values around authority and decision-making within the family may also influence parents' willingness to adopt recommended behaviors for their children.

Furthermore, low educational level poses a significant barrier as it is a determining factor of health level. For children, social pressures and influences may play key roles in successful uptake of intervention activities. Children/teenagers are highly susceptible to peer pressure, and unhealthy dietary choices or sedentary behavior within friend groups can influence individual choices. Social inequalities and limited access to healthy food options, safe spaces for physical activity, and

educational resources in lower-income communities create challenges for adopting healthy lifestyles. Additionally, location of the schools, social and cultural level of pupils, commitment and interest of teachers and school staff may also constitute a barrier.

2.3.3. Degree of Acceptability

The degree of acceptability of interventions/policies for childhood obesity prevention can pose significant barriers to their successful implementation. A significant barrier across Europe is the lack of awareness, understanding and/or acceptance of the severity and consequences of obesity. This often leads to insufficient public support and inadequate funding for prevention programs.

Framing obesity is a key challenge to the successful implementation of related policies/prevention strategies. At European (and global) level, there is a lack of unified disease classification for obesity. Without unified acknowledgement of obesity as a disease, and of the complex factors underlying its etiology, 'successful' public health interventions cannot be delivered. If countries fail to recognize/classify obesity as a complex, chronic disease and continue to focus on weight (and not wider health) governed by 'energy in, energy out' only, it is unlikely the appropriate amount of funding, resources, knowledge, and time will be devoted to effective prevention strategies for obesity.

For the above reason, increased focus is required on intervention strategies beyond nutrition and physical activity, not only to dispel outdated stereotypes that obesity development is solely due to energy balance based on nutrition/physical activity, but also to increase recognition of the complex network of factors that interact to underpin its development (e.g. including sleep, mental health, genetics). Conflicting or weak policies across different sectors, like agriculture, food labelling, or education, can create challenges for a comprehensive and coordinated approach to preventing childhood obesity.

In more general terms, at individual level, perceived burden, lack of perceived need for intervention and stigma/discrimination can also be barriers. Interventions requiring significant time commitment, dietary changes, or participation in unfamiliar activities may be perceived as burdensome and lead to low participation. Individuals, including children and their families, might not recognize the severity or long-term consequences of having poor health (and/or obesity), leading to a lack of motivation to engage in preventive measures. Concerns about potential stigma or discrimination associated with obesity can discourage individuals from seeking help or participating in programs. Public health campaigns or policies that use stigmatizing language or imagery can perpetuate negative stereotypes and discourage affected individuals from seeking support or participating in interventions.

Interventions that do not consider cultural norms, values, religious beliefs, or traditional practices may be less acceptable to the target population. For example, interventions perceived as restrictive or infringing on personal freedom of choice, especially regarding dietary habits, can generate opposition from individuals and communities. Additionally, strategies that fail to acknowledge cultural diversity or tailor interventions to specific cultural contexts may be perceived as irrelevant or inappropriate, undermining their acceptability and effectiveness. Moreover, interventions or policies without meaningful involvement from the affected community may be met with skepticism or distrust. Interventions or policies that require substantial resources, such as funding, personnel, or infrastructure, may face challenges in implementation and sustainability.

At political level, interventions requiring significant policy changes or regulations may face opposition from various stakeholders, including industry groups or individuals concerned about potential economic impacts. Stakeholders may be hesitant to support interventions perceived as excessively expensive or requiring significant financial resources with uncertain long-term benefits. Policymakers require strong evidence bases to make decisions about whether they should implement a proposed intervention. Lack of strong evidence demonstrating the effectiveness or long-term impact of proposed interventions might lead to hesitation from stakeholders to adopt them.

Based on the above, policies must be implemented together with strategies to improve the acceptance from the children, not forcing but leading into joy with healthy food.

2.3.4. Other Implementation Barriers

In the category of the other implementation barriers, PREVENT partners have addressed the health literacy levels of the targeted population. Health literacy is a modifiable yet super-determinant of health that impacts gravely health risk perception (parents or carriers of children, adolescents, etc.) and health self-efficacy determining whether an individual will make a behavioral change or not.

Moreover, inadequate evidence based on the components of 'successful' interventions is a barrier to effective intervention delivery. Researchers across Europe and globally should be aligned in identifying appropriate approaches to addressing obesity, in order to conduct effective research investigations into the most effective obesity prevention strategies. Difficulties in gathering and analyzing accurate data, participation, and impact can hinder program evaluation and improvement. Regarding program evaluation, difficulty in defining clear and measurable outcomes can make it challenging to assess effectiveness and justify continued funding. For the public policy domain, a lack of National Action Plans for childhood obesity prevention is a prominent barrier to the wide implementation of primary obesity prevention strategies at national level.

Another crucial barrier that we had to take into consideration is the economic interest of the food industry and its opposition against any measure that could have an impact on their market. Lastly, PREVENT partners mentioned the "Fast food restaurants" and "Media influences" as other significant barriers, especially for children and adolescents, as they are more vulnerable.

2.3.5. Areas of opportunities/ Opportunities of improvements

Regarding the areas of opportunities/actions that could help to overcome barriers for the successful implementation of Interventions/Policies/Strategies, PREVENT partners pointed out the following:

- **School-Based Interventions:** Strengthening school wellness policies, integrating nutrition and physical education into the curriculum, and promoting healthy food environments in schools support children's health and well-being.
- **Environmental Changes:** Implementing changes in the built environment, such as increasing access to healthy foods, promoting walkable neighborhoods, and creating safe recreational spaces, makes it easier for individuals to engage in healthy behaviors.

- **Technology and Innovation:** Leveraging technology, such as mobile apps, online platforms, and social media, enhances the reach and effectiveness of obesity prevention interventions, especially among younger populations.
- **Enhancing health literacy:** Providing health education and raising awareness about the risks of childhood obesity and the benefits of healthy lifestyles empowers individuals and families to make informed choices and adopt healthier behaviors. Moreover, becomes a public health priority in many countries worldwide including EU member states as well.
- **Communication:** Clear and transparent communication is essential for building trust, addressing concerns, and promoting the benefits of childhood obesity prevention interventions. Effective communication strategies should involve stakeholders at every stage of the process and use culturally appropriate language and channels to reach diverse audiences.
- **Community Engagement:** Involving community members, stakeholders, and organizations in the planning and implementation of interventions fosters a sense of ownership, empowers individuals to actively participate in decision-making on public health strategies, and increases support for obesity prevention efforts. This collaborative approach ensures that interventions are culturally relevant, acceptable, and responsive to the needs and preferences of the target population.
- **Tailoring approaches:** Adapting interventions to fit the cultural context and preferences of the target population increases their acceptability and effectiveness. This involves incorporating cultural beliefs, practices, and norms into program design and delivery to ensure that interventions resonate with individuals and communities. Personalization is a key element in strategies to address obesity, since its etiology is underpinned by a complex network of factors that are not the same for all.
- **Empowerment-centric framing:** Framing interventions around empowerment, positive behavior change, and self-efficacy enhances their acceptability and effectiveness. This approach focuses on building individuals' confidence and skills to make healthy choices, rather than imposing external mandates or restrictions.
- **Framing of 'obesity prevention policies'** is essential as many so-called obesity prevention interventions are aimed at improving health for all. This should be a clear message in their implementation.
- **Cost-effectiveness analysis/evidence needs:** Prioritizing interventions with high return on investment necessitates thorough research to identify crucial components. Understanding which elements contribute most to successful interventions within specific country and population contexts is essential for informed decision-making by intervention developers and policymakers. Interventions should be based on scientific evidence demonstrating their effectiveness in reducing obesity or improving health outcomes. Rigorous evaluation methods, such as randomized controlled trials, can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of interventions. Robust global and regional data on NCDs, best practices for interventions, and cost-effectiveness analysis across diverse contexts are crucial.
- **Funding:** Funding opportunities at EU level may enable member states to invest in primary prevention interventions.
- **Research, monitoring and evaluation:** Investing in research generates evidence on effective strategies, informs decision making, and guides future implementation efforts to ensure the sustainability and impact of obesity prevention initiatives. Furthermore, establishing robust

data collection systems and evaluation frameworks enables stakeholders to track progress, identify areas for improvement, and demonstrate the impact of childhood obesity prevention interventions. This feedback loop ensures accountability, transparency, and continuous quality improvement.

- **Policy Advocacy:** Advocating for evidence-based policies at local, regional, and national levels can create supportive environments for healthy eating and physical activity, leading to systemic changes that promote obesity prevention. The development of strict and clear laws can limit the harm of the food industry. Policy changes at the local, state, and national levels can address systemic factors contributing to childhood obesity and create lasting improvements in population health.
- **Multi-sectoral collaboration:** Engaging with diverse stakeholders, including government agencies, healthcare providers, schools, businesses, community organizations, urban planning, transportation, agriculture, and the food industry, fosters a comprehensive and coordinated approach to childhood obesity prevention. Collaboration ensures that interventions address the social, economic, and environmental determinants of health and leverage the collective expertise and resources of diverse stakeholders to achieve common goals. In addition, public-private partnerships are essential as well. Collaboration with private sectors not only shares financial burdens but also leverages the expertise and resources of both sectors, leading to more comprehensive and sustainable solutions for childhood obesity prevention.

It is also pointed out that the proposed areas of opportunities should be considered within the context of the WHO's Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) framework and Healthier Together, the EU NCDs initiative which outlines a comprehensive approach to addressing NCDs like obesity across the EU. Complementing Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, the EU NCD Initiative is a pillar of the European Health Union. The EU approach to the challenge of NCDs involves an integrated response across all sectors and policy fields - an integrated response to obesity prevention at European, national and local level is crucial.

There is also a major opportunity for obesity to have a voice in the new "Joint Action to Prevent NCDs and Cancer (sic)" which started 1/1/2024 (PREVENT partners should review this opportunity, <https://www.preventncd.eu/>). However, a strong evidence base and wide collaboration between all stakeholders is necessary.

2.4. Remarks and Conclusions of the survey

The survey implemented in the three demo countries, where the PREVENT Living Labs will operate, showed that currently there is a wide variety of **interventions and policies** related to primary prevention of childhood and adolescent obesity. Their goal is the promotion of healthy dietary habits and regular physical activity with a simultaneous reduction of sedentary lifestyle, under the general concept of promoting a healthy and active lifestyle during childhood and adolescence. Many of the interventions/policies implement a multidisciplinary and multilevel approach also addressing the environment of the child and the family. All reported interventions/policies were considered relevant to proceed to the next phase of PREVENT.

In terms of **health outcomes** targeted, the majority of the selected interventions and policies, as expected, do not have a specific health outcome targeted, but a general target such as the overall optimal physical, mental, emotional and social health, optimal growth and development as well as the overall well-being of the children. Additionally, the improvement of fitness levels, as well as long-term

outcomes, such as prevention of obesity and chronic diseases later in life are reported. For interventions with more specific outcomes, such as prevention of obesity during childhood, anthropometric indices (e.g body height, weight, waist circumference) are self-reported or measured to assess overweight and obesity (assessed by body mass index), but also measurements of physical activity frequency and intensity, dietary assessment measures and quality of life measures are also included.

The intervention/policies in two of the three countries **did not apply a behavioural model**. In Spain, several interventions applied/apply a behavioral model such as the **Transtheoretical model, Motivational interviewing, Positive parenting, the ASE Model, as well as the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Resilience theory. Co-creation participatory methods** were either used (Spain) or implied (Greece, Spain) as the successful implementation of the interventions/policies involves effective collaboration among various stakeholders. However, there is a great area of improvement in the use of both a behavioural model or co-creation participatory methods in the implementation of the current interventions and policies on prevention of obesity in the childhood and adolescence in the three countries.

Most of the interventions reported are implemented in the **school setting**, and some in **primary health care centres** and **the whole community**. Policies are covering schools and the whole community and society in many instances.

The main **target population across the countries** for the policies/interventions are primarily children and adolescents. Adults that influence children's decisions and choices, such as parents/guardians and teachers are also involved in the intervention. Other target populations mentioned, are professionals working with children, all citizens, businesses, users of digital services, companies and organizations that use or provide audio-visual or media services.

Stakeholders form a long list of: public health institutions and agencies responsible for designing and implementing public policies, governmental authorities, school administrators, managers of school canteens and cafeterias offering schools' meals, municipalities and local authorities, the food industry, food suppliers, stores, advertisers, marketing practitioners, health care services, media companies, civil society organizations technology companies, tech industry associations and trade groups, environmental groups, advocacy groups, citizens, academics and researchers.

The interventions/policies usually cover **both public and private sector** and they are **currently in effect** with variable length of duration since initiation ranging from 2 years to up to more than 80 years since certain relevant regulations date back to 1937.

A variety of **materials and tools** are used for the implementation of the interventions and policies. In terms of their aim and content, they can generally be grouped in those that have an **educational scope** (webinars, workshop, videos, guides, toolboxes, etc), those that aim to **raise awareness and motivation** (eating challenges, diary logs, motivational messages, etc), those that facilitate or provide **access to healthy food and physical activity** opportunities (provision of fruits at schools, instalment of instruments for exercise, etc) and those that are used to **monitor and measure** exposures and outcomes, usually for the purposes of research.

Overall, traditional tools such as **printed materials are used**, although **digitalization of the tools is widely implemented**. Thus, a wide variety of **digital tools and materials** are used in several forms, such as:

- a) Online educational webinars, workshops, courses
- b) Online applications (e.g. for entering school menu information and extracting evaluation reports based on recommended criteria)
- c) Online platforms
- d) Diaries for monitoring commitments or challenge calendars
- e) Application in WhatsApp/cell phones
- f) Animated cartoons with interactive materials
- g) Media data spaces
- h) Virtual and augmented reality tools
- i) Hotlines
- j) Infographics
- k) Toolboxes for promoting healthy lifestyles and/or monitoring physical activity.

Other material and tools such as public consultations, stakeholder dialogues, in person webinars & workshops, activity and healthy spaces modules and family activities are implemented.

Regarding the legal framework, the majority of the interventions/policies are supported by either a **national or European legal framework**, while **the existence of enforcement methods does not seem to be the norm** for all interventions/policies. The **funding** of the interventions/policies seems to be mostly **public and/or with EU sources**.

When it comes to monitoring mechanisms, the results of the survey across the three countries are variable ranging from **no monitoring mechanism in place** for the majority of the selected interventions/policies in one country (Greece), to the **existence of a monitoring mechanism** for all interventions/policies in the other countries (Spain, Sweden) including a self-monitoring tool in one of them.

With respect to the **barriers/obstacles** identified, in all three demo countries **combined, financial/cost constraints** were **the most prevalent**, followed by **barriers related to the degree of acceptability** and then **by socio/cultural constraints**.

With respect to **financial/cost** barriers the **main problems** are related to lack of financial resources for:

- a) Hiring and training personnel (e.g. nutritionists, public health specialist and other professionals)
- b) Purchasing materials and tools needed (e.g. materials for workshops, cost of meals)
- c) Sustaining and maintaining premises and infrastructure (e.g. cost for electricity, repairs)
- d) Acquiring tools for promotion and dissemination of information to the community and the public about the intervention/policy (e.g. cost of campaigns, creation of digital materials and platforms)
- e) Continuing educational activities for teachers, parents and other targeted populations

- f) Making structural changes and building the infrastructure needed for the schools (e.g. cafeterias, canteens, playgrounds) and the change of obesogenic environment (e.g. lanes, parks)
- g) Applying enforcement and monitoring (e.g. compliance mechanisms, etc.)
- h) Implementing studies for assessing the effectiveness of the intervention/policy (e.g. conduct formal evaluation of the program)
- i) Sustaining the intervention for longer period of time

With respect to the barriers related to the **degree of acceptability** the **main problems** identified are to the following:

- a) Lack of information provided to schools about the intervention or the policy
- b) Lack of awareness among parents and the society in understanding the impact of obesity on child's health and well-being
- c) Not adequate prioritization of the intervention within the school program
- d) Not fully accepted by the teachers because of lack of time and/or negative mindset
- e) Not fully accepted by the parents due to different perceptions about obesity
- f) Not fully accepted by relevant stakeholders (school management, canteen managers, etc.)
- g) Lack of interest on behalf of the child
- h) Students do not consume menus with healthier foods that they don't like
- i) Unlimited advertising of unhealthy products targeting children

With respect to the barriers related to **social/cultural constraints** the **main problems** identified are the following:

- a) Lack of understanding from students and their families about the necessity to make healthier menus in schools due to different attitudes towards ideal body weight and body image
- b) Unhealthy foods are seen by parents as an act of love towards their children.
- c) Different perceptions about obesity among families from disadvantaged neighborhoods with higher vulnerability and conflict
- d) Expectation of a "classic diet therapy" with an informative/prescriptive model from health professionals, rather than a "preventive" changing of lifestyle approach
- e) Students with different cultural backgrounds and different dietary habits do not easily accept proposed changes for healthier choice of foods
- f) Aggressive food marketing and especially extensive promotion and marketing of ultra-processed food.
- g) Negative influences by the media

With respect to the **other barriers** identified, not included in the above-mentioned categories, the following were reported:

- a) Lack of sustainability actions incorporated in the design phase of the intervention before its implementation
- b) No continuity in informing/educating the public and the relevant stakeholders
- c) Lack of coordination and cooperation between relevant stakeholders for the successful implementation and evaluation of the intervention/policy
- d) Unsuccessful dissemination efforts in reaching all nutrition-related professions.
- e) Lack of an organizational system to monitor the implementation of the intervention/policy
- f) Dietary guidelines not systematically integrated with nutrition education programs at the schools and the food served in the canteens.
- g) Lack of actions to raise awareness among parents and professionals
- h) Existence of digital divide
- i) Insufficient adaptation to rapid technological changes
- j) Need to ensure privacy protection
- k) Not adequate balance between ensuring safety with privacy rights and addressing emerging online risks
- l) Lack of food business networks that offer healthy food
- m) No adequate research available for providing evidence on the effectiveness of interventions/policies
- n) Health crises, such as COVID-19 pandemic, can hamper the implementation of interventions.

The above list of barriers can be complemented by some additional important barriers reported by the WP2 PREVENT partners. Please note that the full report of the WP2 PREVENT partners that have answered the short survey questionnaire focusing only on the identification of barriers can be found in section 4 of this Report.

Thus, some **financial/cost barriers** were pointed out concerning the **funding of projects** related to obesity:

- At EU level:
 - a) Obesity is recognized as Non-Communicable Disease and needs to be framed as a chronic, relapsing disease
 - b) Complex processes for funding exist
 - c) Bureaucratic procedures delay/complicate funding allocation for new/developing interventions
- At the national level:
 - a) Governments face competing priorities for allocating limited budgets

b) Within government agencies, resources may be allocated unevenly, with a greater emphasis on therapy rather than prevention of obesity, and with no consistency across regions of the same country

- Implementation costs vary based on national funding
- Most interventions require direct financial investment to provide resources/infrastructure
- Technological platforms/equipment used to enhance these interventions add to overall implementation cost
- Short-term funding cycles, no stable funding and budget uncertainties undermine the sustainability of obesity prevention initiatives
- Inability of funding sustainably interventions for low-income families and communities e.g. offering meals at schools, reimbursing the purchase of specific products per age group, or hold nutrition education programs for families.

More issues related to *social disparities in health* were stressed, as follows:

- Families with lower socioeconomic status may have limited access to healthy foods, safe outdoor spaces for physical activity, and healthcare services.
- Economic constraints can also make healthier options less affordable.

With respect to **social and cultural barriers**, besides the ones related to differences in attitudes and perceptions about body image and ideal body size, parents' knowledge regarding healthy eating and physical activity, and adherence to food traditions and practices that may not align with dietary recommendations, reported also by partners in the three demo countries, the following were highlighted:

- Participation in physical activity programs, especially for girls or adolescents, may be hindered by different social norms regarding physical activity.
- Family structures and cultural expectations around child-rearing practices may influence physical activity levels and dietary choices.
- Cultural values around authority and decision-making within the family may also influence parents' willingness to adopt recommended behaviors for their children.
- Peer pressure can influence individual choices related to dietary choices or sedentary behavior.
- Low educational level poses a significant barrier as it is a determining factor of health level.
- Limited access to healthy food options, safe spaces for physical activity, and educational resources in lower-income communities create challenges for adopting healthy lifestyles.
- Location of the school.

With respect to **acceptability barriers**, the following additional barriers were highlighted:

- Without unified acknowledgement of obesity as a disease, and of the complex factors underlying its etiology, 'successful' public health interventions cannot be delivered

- Interventions that do not consider cultural norms, values, religious beliefs, or traditional practices may be less acceptable to the target population.
- Interventions requiring significant policy changes or regulations may face opposition from various stakeholders,
- At political level, interventions requiring significant policy changes or regulations may face opposition from various stakeholders, including industry groups or individuals concerned about potential economic impacts.

With respect to **other barriers**, the following additional barriers were highlighted:

- Low health literacy levels of the targeted population
- Economic interest of the food industry and its opposition against any measure that could have an impact on their market
- Fast food restaurants culture prevails
- Negative media influences

Issues related to barriers for **research** on childhood obesity:

- Inadequate evidence based on the components of 'successful' interventions.
- Difficulties in gathering and analyzing accurate data.
- Difficulty in defining clear and measurable outcomes regarding program evaluation.

Issues related to the **public policy** domain:

- Lack of National Action Plans for childhood obesity prevention

It should be noted that some of the observed barriers can be considered belonging to more than one category of barriers, e.g. issues related to socio-economic status, can be grouped to social barriers as well as to acceptability barriers. So, some barriers can be found in both large categories.

With respect to the **domains** that barriers were grouped in (see Appendix 1/Table 2), most of the barriers were grouped in more than one domain, confirming the complexity of obesity etiology and prevention. It seems that the childcare and school domain, the community and built environment domain, the society and public policy domain were the domains most frequently involved. Nevertheless, it is also evident that all domains are equally important and that efforts to overcome effectively the observed barriers should include all the related domains.

Based on the above, **opportunities and actions** have been proposed in order to overcome barriers. The following common suggestions were reported by partners in the three demo countries:

- a) Increase **financial support**,
- b) **Enhance health literacy** by providing health education and raising awareness the benefits of healthy lifestyles and the risks of overweight and obesity,
- c) Increase the **use of digital tools and technology**,
- d) **Use wider dissemination channels to promote** interventions/policies to target audiences,

- e) **Use of co-creation participatory methods with an equity perspective,**
- f) **Introduce more regulatory aspects especially for food advertisement and marketing,**
- g) **Conduct more relevant research.**

Additionally, PREVENT partners proposed that obesity prevention interventions/policies should have the following characteristics:

- a) An **empowerment-centric framing:** aiming to empowerment and positive behavior change and focusing on building individuals' confidence and skills to make healthy choices, rather than imposing external mandates or restrictions.
- b) A **tailored to the characteristics of the target population approach:** adapting interventions to fit the cultural context and preferences of the target population allowing for personalization of the intervention.
- c) An **“engaging the community” approach:** involving community members, stakeholders, and organizations in the planning and implementation of interventions. This collaborative approach ensures that interventions are culturally relevant, acceptable, and responsive to the needs and preferences of the target population.
- d) **Incorporation of technology and innovation:** enhances the reach and effectiveness of obesity prevention interventions, especially among younger populations.
- e) **Incorporation of effective communication strategies:** clear, transparent, and culturally appropriate communication builds trust, addresses concerns, and promotes the benefits of childhood obesity prevention interventions.
- f) **Collaboration with multiple sectors and relevant stakeholders:** collaboration ensures that interventions address the social, economic, and environmental determinants of health and leverage the collective expertise and resources of diverse stakeholders to achieve common goals. Public-private partnerships are considered essential.
- g) **Advocacy for supportive policies:** Advocating for evidence-based policies at local, regional, and national levels can create supportive environments for healthy eating and physical activity, leading to systemic changes that promote obesity prevention.

Table 4. Main types of barriers/obstacles to the implementation of selected Interventions/Policies/Strategies in Greece, Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
Greece				
National Food-based dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents	Lack of funding impaired: a) the wider dissemination of the guidelines b) the continuity of the educational programs and activities	-Families with different dietary habits due to different cultural backgrounds (e.g., immigrants) may not adhere to the guidelines. - Underprivileged populations and those with low socio-economic status	There is no monitoring on the degree of acceptability.	- No continuity of guidelines' dissemination to the public was established. - Guidelines did not reach many related to nutrition health professionals. - Guidelines were available from the Hellenic Institution of Educational policies, but there is no

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
	promoting guidelines' implementation	may not have adequate access to the guidelines and may not understand them.		regularly collected information about their actual dissemination to the schools. - Guidelines were not systematically integrated with nutrition education programs at the schools as well as the food served in the canteens. -No information about the effectiveness of national food-based guidelines in terms of achieving their final goal, such as adherence to healthier dietary habits, or change towards healthier nutritional choices.
School Canteen Standards	Lack of funding for regular information of students/ parents about the products sold in the canteens and their connection with health and well-being.	None reported	The variety of healthy options sold by the canteens is not so popular among students.	- School administration use the money earned from renting the canteens as an income to reinforce their budget. Profit is their main consideration and not so much the adherence to the Standards. - Monitoring of adherence to the Standards by the relevant public officers is not frequent and adequately effective. - Standards are not integrated with nutrition education programs at the schools and promotion of healthy diet
WHO Child Growth Standards	None reported	None reported	None reported	-A wider implementation to parents and the general public is required in order to understand their importance and importance for monitoring growth.
The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme	None Reported	None reported	None Reported	-Time delays exist regarding the start and the implementation of the individual actions of the program s -Problematic cooperation between school units and the competent authorities implementing the program, as well as its selected contractors
Public information campaign on nutrition	Lack of funding which impaired the wide implementation of the campaign and its sustainability	Lack of cultural adaptation	None reported	Additional communication channels are required for the wider disseminations of the campaign.
Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools-Nutrition Education	None Reported	None Reported	None Reported	- Optional use of the material - Materials are not very interesting for the students - No evidence of its effectiveness in terms of behavioral change
Spain-Catalonia				

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
The Daily Mile	None Reported	None Reported	-Schools are not adequately informed about the project. - The acceptance of the project is difficult if headmasters do not prioritize its implementation - The project has not always the full acceptance by the teachers (their time and mind-set for these kinds of activities can become barriers)	None Reported
Active Pauses	None Reported	None Reported	-Schools are not adequately informed about the project. - The acceptance of the project is difficult if headmasters do not prioritize its implementation - The project has not always the full acceptance by the teachers (their time and mind-set for these kinds of activities can become barriers)	None Reported
School Menus Review Programme: More Healthy and Sustainable School Canteens (PreME-MEMSS)	-Cost/financing constraints exist since cost is covered by Barcelona City Council and two Public Health Agencies. - Experts are needed to review the school menus - Certain demands made by schools cannot be met. -More personnel is needed to implement Phase 3 of the menu reviews.	-Families do not fully understand why certain changes are made to school menus. -Students are also reluctant to make certain changes to the menu. -Cultural customs can make it difficult to accept the changes proposed by the program - Children are continuously exposed to food marketing and influenced by media.	-The acceptance of the programme by the agents involved (school management, management company, canteen monitors, teachers, families) varies from school to school as well as coordination between the agents.	-The program does not reach pre-school facilities - There is lack of regulation on healthy and sustainable school menus -Untrained monitoring equipment in children's diet-health -Sale of unhealthy products at the school environment
Prevention and management of childhood obesity in the neighbourhood La Mina (La Mina)	-Professionals are needed for the personalized intervention, preparation of materials, time / training needs for health professionals and stakeholders.	-Many families participating in the project do not perceive childhood obesity as a health problem. -Unhealthy foods are seen as an act of love towards their children. - Families often expect a process of "classic diet	-Lack of interest on the part of the child.	- Entry into the community was practically null during 2021 due to covid-19 -The lack of dedicated time for professionals who are overworked. -Limits related to the poverty index, to the obesogenic environment, to

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
	- More funding is needed for structural changes necessary to reduce obesogenic environments	therapy" with an informative/prescriptive model from health professionals -Aggressive marketing of fast food and the ultra-processed industry.		social and cultural determinants, level of neighborhood conflict -Lack of coordination and agreed objectives regarding the prevention of obesity in the network of stakeholders -Lack of food business networks that offer healthy food -Lack of sustainability actions designed from the beginning of the project.
INFADIMED	-Investment is needed for human resources to replace the nurse who performs the intervention -Funding is needed for workshop material in schools and communities -Funding is needed to promote the program among the community -Funding is needed to evaluate interventions.	Extensive promotion and marketing of ultra-processed food.	There are no limits to the advertising of unhealthy products in the children's population. There is no regulation that prohibits it.	None reported
SEEDS (Science Engagement to Empower Disadvantaged Adolescents)	None reported	Adaptation is needed depending on the sociocultural characteristics of each country and population included.	None reported	COVID-19 pandemic made it difficult to enter schools, and to meet with families for parts of the intervention.
SEISMO	Sustainability of investment of private/public funding during a minimum of 6 years per each school is difficult.	None reported	None reported	None reported
Sweden				
The Swedish Radio and Television Act	- <i>Enforcement and Monitoring</i> : Ensuring compliance with the Act requires robust monitoring mechanisms, overseeing a diverse media landscape (traditional and digital channels)	None reported	-Satellite channels broadcasted from other countries not subject to the same Swedish advertising ban and restrictions on children's advertisements cannot be enforced. - <i>Balancing Freedom of Expression</i> : While the Act aims to shield children from harmful content, individuals' rights to express themselves through	- <i>Limited Scope for Digital Platforms</i> : Digital sharing platforms, such as YouTube, operate in a different landscape and may require separate regulations to address their unique challenges. - <i>Emerging Technologies</i> : The Act has not been adopted to include regulations for new media formats, streaming services, and online content platforms.

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
			<p>the media must be respected.</p> <p>- Food advertisements are not specifically mentioned in the Act. However, other legislation and self-regulatory mechanisms may apply.</p>	
The Swedish Marketing Act	Barriers exist related to costs, taxes, and competitive regulations.	None reported	<p>-Food advertising is not specifically addressed, however food advertisements must follow relevant guidelines, such as: regulations for advertising to minors; prohibition of specific advertisement methods (subliminal messaging, spam, direct marketing), etc.</p>	None reported
The Digital Service Act (DSA)	<p><i>-Enforcement and Monitoring:</i> Ensuring compliance with ad targeting rules requires robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms.</p>	None reported	<p><i>-Balancing Protection and Innovation:</i> Striking a balance between safeguarding children from harmful content and allowing age-appropriate innovation is complex.</p> <p><i>-Defining “Child” and “Teen”:</i> This distinction should be made in order to apply targeted advertising restrictions effectively.</p> <p><i>-Contextual Advertising:</i> The DSA allows for contextual advertising, which is based on the content of the webpage or app rather than individual user profiles. Thus, sponsored content can still be targeted to children.</p> <p><i>-Parental Consent:</i> If a platform obtains explicit parental consent, it may show targeted ads to minors, however, this consent process must be transparent and</p>	<p><i>-Adaptability to Evolving Platforms:</i> The Act need to adapt to new forms of content and advertising</p>

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
			<p>comply with data protection regulations.</p> <p><i>-Age Verification:</i> Platforms can use age verification mechanisms to determine whether a user is a minor. If a user is verified as an adult, targeted ads may be shown.</p> <p><i>-Public Health Campaigns:</i> Ads related to health and safety, such as vaccination awareness or healthy eating, may still be targeted to minors.</p> <p><i>-Non-Commercial Content:</i> Content that is not directly commercial, such as public service announcements or educational material, is exempt from these restrictions</p>	
The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code	<p><i>-Resource Constraints:</i> Self-regulatory bodies that oversee the implementation of the Code may face resource constraints, which can limit their effectiveness.</p>	None reported	<p><i>- Global Applicability vs Local Context:</i> While the ICC Code is designed to be globally applicable, there can be challenges in interpreting and applying it in distinct cultural and legal contexts.</p>	<p><i>-Awareness and Understanding:</i> Not all businesses, especially smaller ones, may be aware of the ICC Code or fully understand its guidelines. This can lead to non-compliance due to lack of knowledge.</p> <p><i>- Diverse and Evolving Marketing Practices:</i> Keeping the Code up-to-date with recent technologies and platforms is be challenging.</p> <p><i>- Enforcement:</i> The ICC Code is self-regulatory, meaning businesses are expected to adhere to it voluntarily. Thus, enforcement can be challenging.</p> <p><i>- Digital Complexity:</i> With the rise of digital marketing, there are complexities around data privacy, consent, and transparency that can pose challenges to the implementation of the Code.</p>
The Audiovisual and Media Policy	None Reported	None reported	<p><i>- Diverse Media Landscape:</i> The media landscape in the EU is diverse, with different languages, cultures, and traditions. This</p>	<p><i>- Technological Changes:</i> The policy needs to adapt to new technological changes.</p> <p><i>- Competition with Global Players:</i> European media companies face</p>

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
			<p>diversity can make it challenging to implement a uniform policy across all member states.</p> <p>- <i>Regulatory Challenges</i>: The policy faces regulatory challenges, such as the need to balance the free movement of services with the protection of cultural diversity.</p>	<p>stiff competition from global players.</p> <p>- <i>Legal Constraints</i>: The policy operates within the constraints of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which does not provide for any direct powers in audiovisual and media policy.</p> <p>- <i>Digital and Green Transitions</i>: The policy aims to help industry embrace the digital and green transitions. However, these transitions can pose challenges, such as the need for investment and the development of new skills.</p>
The School meal system	-The cost of food and electricity has risen significantly	None reported	<p>- It is considered appropriate to serve meals that are not 100% in line with nutritional guidelines in primary schools if it means that pupils are happier and are not going hungry, and there is less food waste. It is a tough balancing act to change menus while still ensuring that pupils eat.</p> <p>- It is deemed acceptable that pupils over a certain age can leave the premises.</p> <p>-It is deemed acceptable that these pupils have choice and access to fast food restaurants/other establishments selling unhealthy foods and beverages (i.e., convenience stores, etc.).</p> <p>- It is deemed acceptable to provide vouchers without oversight to upper secondary pupils as many of them are legally adults.</p>	None reported
The European school fruit vegetables and milk scheme	None Reported	None Reported	-The implementation of the scheme has been very heterogeneous, which means that EU students do not benefit equally from it.	<p>-The lack of continuity in the execution and the sparse number of days of fruits and vegetables deliveries, could limit its potential benefits.</p> <p>-Administrative burden.</p>

	Types of barriers/obstacles			
	Cost/Financing	Social/Cultural	Degree of Acceptability	Other Implementation Barriers
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raising awareness within the school and the student community. - Connection with school nurses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Covid-19 Pandemic impact. -Fruit types to be distributed. -Coordination of food distribution and food waste. -Long term scalability.
Safer Internet Centre Sweden	None Reported	None Reported	None reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Raise awareness among parents and professionals - The Center should bridge the digital divide - The Center should be adapted to the rapid technological changes, - The Center should ensure privacy protection - The Center should coordinate multi-stakeholder efforts, evaluating impact, and navigating legal complexities - The Center should balance safety with privacy rights and address emerging online risks -This intervention does not include specific details about food advertising or advertising to kids.

Table 5. Distribution of barriers/obstacles to the implementation of selected interventions/policies/strategies in Greece, Spain (Catalonia) and Sweden by domain of implementation

	Barriers/obstacles by domain of implementation					
	Individual Domain	Family and Peers Domain	Childcare and School Domain	Community and Built Environment Domain	Society Domain	Public Policy Domain
Greece						
National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
School Canteen Standards	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
WHO Child Growth Standards	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme			✓	✓	✓	✓
Public information campaign on nutrition				✓	✓	✓
Health education programs for students in secondary schools	✓	✓	✓			
Spain- Catalonia						

	Barriers/obstacles by domain of implementation					
	Individual Domain	Family and Peers Domain	Childcare and School Domain	Community and Built Environment Domain	Society Domain	Public Policy Domain
The Daily Mile			✓		✓	✓
Active Pauses			✓		✓	✓
School Menus Review Programme: More Healthy and Sustainable School Canteens (PreME-MEMSS)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Prevention and management of childhood obesity in the neighborhood La Mina (La Mina)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
INFADIMED			✓	✓	✓	✓
SEEDS (Science Engagement to Empower Disadvantaged Adolescents)	✓	✓	✓		✓	
SEISMO						✓
Sweden						
The Swedish Radio and Television Act				✓	✓	✓
The Swedish Marketing Act					✓	✓
The Digital Service Act (DSA)					✓	✓
The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code				✓	✓	✓
The Audiovisual and Media Policy					✓	✓
School meal system	✓	✓	✓	✓		
The European school fruit vegetables and milk scheme	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Safer Internet Centre Sweden		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

3. Metrics for assessing PREVENT's primary interventions

As outlined in many reports, there are over 100 factors that contribute to childhood obesity and these are often interdependent. Despite high-quality, international and longitudinal research programmes relevant to childhood obesity, integrating and monitoring multi-level system factors still presents a challenge. For example, The Childhood Obesity Surveillance Initiative (COSI) from the World Health Organisation (WHO), collects individual-level data on anthropometry, dietary and physical activity patterns, screen time, and sleep, among others. Recent findings from 6 to 9-year-olds in the WHO European Region demonstrates substantial country-level differences in healthy and unhealthy dietary habits, with patterns that cannot be fully explained. To better monitor change over time and evaluate the effects of an intervention, data is needed at the level of the child and their family, at the level of the school and at the community level. To successfully source, store, retrieve, analyse, and present the socioeconomic, health, dietary, economic and geospatial data needed in an intervention, a number of considerations are required to meet legal, data protection, privacy and ethical requirements in addition to the necessary standards, protocols and technological aspects. However, it is also important to acknowledge that obesity is the outcome of a complex adaptive system and the success of any intervention is dependent on the wider social context in which is employed and embedded.

Therefore, assessing primary interventions targeting the reduction and prevention of childhood obesity requires a comprehensive set of indicators that cover various domains. These indicators can be categorized into qualitative and quantitative metrics, each providing valuable insights into the effectiveness, acceptability, and sustainability of the interventions. Below is a set of indicators organized by domain:

Table 6. Metrics to assess PREVENT's primary interventions.

GOAL AREA	KPIs	TYPE
Economic Assessment	Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (CER): The cost per unit of health outcome (e.g., cost per BMI reduction).	Quantitative
	Return on Investment (ROI): The financial return compared to the investment in the intervention.	Quantitative
	Healthcare Cost Savings: Reduction in healthcare costs due to decreased incidence of obesity-related conditions.	Quantitative
	Program Implementation Costs: Total costs associated with the delivery and maintenance of the intervention.	Quantitative
	Stakeholder Perceptions of Value: Feedback from stakeholders (e.g., policymakers, funders) on the perceived economic benefits of the intervention.	Qualitative

Social-Related Validation	Participation Rates: Percentage of the target population engaging with the intervention.	Quantitative
	Changes in Physical Activity Levels, Sleep, Screen time: Measured through surveys or wearable devices.	Quantitative
	Nutritional Intake Improvements: Changes in dietary patterns assessed via food frequency questionnaires, 24 hour recalls or food registers.	Quantitative
	Analysis of stages (% in each one, changes over time, etc) via the administration of short questionnaires assessing specific conduct and the stages of change. (transtheoretical change model)	Quantitative
	Community Support: Level of community backing and involvement in the intervention.	Qualitative
	Participant Satisfaction: Feedback from children and parents regarding the intervention's acceptability and impact on their lives.	Qualitative
	Behavioral Changes: Observations and self-reports on changes in lifestyle behaviors.	Qualitative
User Acceptability	Retention Rates: Proportion of participants who complete the intervention.	Quantitative
	Compliance Rates: Adherence to prescribed activities or dietary guidelines.	Quantitative
	Perceived Ease of Participation: Participants' views on the convenience and feasibility of engaging in the intervention.	Qualitative
	Cultural Relevance: Degree to which the intervention is perceived as culturally appropriate and sensitive.	Qualitative
	Feedback on Intervention Components: Specific feedback on different elements of the intervention (e.g., educational materials, activities).	Qualitative
	Degree of codesign and participation in elaboration of proposed actions	Qualitative
Sustainability Factors	Long-term Health Outcomes: Monitoring health outcomes (e.g., BMI, obesity rates) over several years post-intervention.	Quantitative
	Resource Allocation: Ongoing availability of resources (financial, human, infrastructure) to support the intervention.	Quantitative
	Institutionalization of Practices: Extent to which intervention practices are integrated into routine school or community activities.	Qualitative
	Policy Integration: Degree to which the intervention aligns with and is supported by existing policies.	Qualitative

Compatibility with Existing Policy Schemes	Alignment with National/Local Health Goals: Degree of alignment with broader public health objectives.	Quantitative
	Funding and Support Metrics: Amount and sources of funding and institutional support for the intervention.	Quantitative
	Policy Maker and Stakeholder Buy-In: Level of endorsement and support from policymakers and influential stakeholders.	Qualitative
	Regulatory Compliance: Degree to which the intervention adheres to relevant regulations and guidelines.	Qualitative
Comprehensive Evaluation Framework	Mixed-Methods Approach: Utilizing both qualitative and quantitative data to gain a holistic understanding of the intervention's impact.	Quantitative & Qualitative
	Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: Regularly updating and assessing indicators to adapt and improve the intervention.	

By employing this diverse set of indicators, public health professionals can effectively assess the multifaceted impact of primary interventions aimed at reducing and preventing childhood obesity, ensuring they are economically viable, socially accepted, user-friendly, sustainable, and aligned with existing policy frameworks.

4. Conclusions

In summary, our findings from the meta-analysis using various definitions for obesity in childhood and adolescence provide evidence that obesity seems to increase the odds for 10 cancer types in adulthood. We were also able to provide a list of somatometrics in children and adolescents that associate obesity to cancer in adult life.

Furthermore, in terms of health outcomes targeted, most of the selected interventions and policies, as expected, do not have a specific health outcome targeted, but a general target such as the overall optimal physical, mental, emotional and social health, optimal growth and development as well as the overall well-being of the children. Additionally, the improvement of fitness levels, as well as long-term outcomes, such as prevention of obesity and chronic diseases later in life are reported.

A preliminary set of indicators for assessing primary interventions have been provided with the contribution of CoPs in each node in order for each country to adapt what indicators best fit their priorities, needs and political framework. Future research must therefore examine how best to incorporate both quantitatively driven, macro-level indicators and qualitative data, which is more appropriate for capturing the wider context and lived experiences of children or communities for whom obesity interventions may be implemented.

Appendix 1. Survey Questionnaire

PREVENT - Questionnaire to identify current interventions, policies, and strategies for the prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence as well as limitations and barriers in their implementation

Information Sheet

PREVENT is a collaborative EU-funded Action to Improve and Upscale Primary Prevention of Cancer by Addressing Childhood Obesity. Through diligent implementation research and a comprehensive approach, PREVENT aims to lay the foundation for a future where healthier lifestyles and brighter tomorrows await every child. It is supported and funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe program. More info can be found on our website: <https://preventproject.eu/>.

The purpose of this questionnaire, which was developed by the National Public Health Organization of Greece, a PREVENT partner, in the context of Task 2.2 of WP2, is to gather information on the current interventions, policies and strategies that are implemented in your country in relation to the primary prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence. An additional purpose of the questionnaire is the identification of limitations, barriers or obstacles that have been observed during the implementation of each of the interventions/policies/strategies identified, with the final goal to find ways to overcome them. Your participation will contribute to our project's delivery of the initial PREVENT multi-actor and context aware primary interventions. This is an anonymous questionnaire.

Questions marked with an "*" are mandatory.

Please, provide information for as **many interventions/policies/strategies are currently implemented in your country** for the **prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence**. You can repeat the questionnaire for each intervention/policy/strategy you describe. We focus on primary prevention of obesity and the age range 9-16 years of age. Please limit the responses for open-ended questions to a maximum of 5 -10 sentences.

1. Provide the Title/Name of the intervention/Policy/Strategy*

(Please provide the whole title/name and not only acronyms. If there isn't a specific name, provide a general title of the intervention/policy/strategy) [text]

2. Indicate which type it refers to: *

- Intervention
- Policy
- Strategy
- Don't Know

3. To which scale/context is this Intervention/Policy/Strategy being implemented? *

(Please select all that apply)

- School
- Child-care (i.e., Nursery Schools)
- Family

- Sports (i.e., Federations, Leagues, Clubs)
- Community (e.g., Civic Centres, Games Libraries, Libraries, Recreation Centres, Scouts, etc.)
- Clinical setting (e.g., Primary Care Health Centres, Outpatient Clinics, etc.)
- Whole society (e.g., Mass Media, Municipal Markets, etc.)
- Public policy
- Other (please specify):

4. Please add any additional observations and comments you may have: [text]

5. What is the Intervention/Policy/Strategy? *[text]

6. Which are the main objectives? *[text]

7. What is the main health outcome? *[text]

8. Which are the target populations? *[text]

9. Which are the target stakeholders? *[text]

10. What is the respective context/place of implementation? *[text]

11. Are co-creation/participatory methods applied? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

12. If yes, please describe how, frequency and with whom? [text]

13. Is a model of behavioral change applied? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

14. If yes, which one(s) and how are they applied/evaluated?

15. Which is/are the material(s)/tool(s) used? *

16. Which is the estimated duration of the Intervention/Policy/Strategy? *

16.1. How many months (please fill in a number)?

16.2. How many years (please fill in a number)?

16.3. What is the start date? (i.e., DD-MM-YYYY or MM-YYYY)

16.4. Please add any additional observation and comments you may have [text]

17. What is the level of implementation of the Intervention/Policy/Strategy? *

- National
- Regional
- Local
- Other (please specify) [text]

18. Does the Intervention/Policy/Strategy have the support (economic, logistic, technical, etc.) of government administration? (local, municipal, regional, etc.) * [text]

19. Does the Intervention/Policy/Strategy focus on public or private settings? *

- Public only
- Private only
- Both public and private
- Don't know

20. Does the Intervention/Policy/Strategy use digital tools and infrastructure for its implementation? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

21. If yes, please specify: [text]

22. Please add any additional observations and comments you may have: [text]

23. Is the Intervention/Policy/Strategy supported by a legal framework? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

24. If yes, please specify: [text]

25. Is the Intervention/Policy/Strategy enforced by any means? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

26. If yes, please provide information on how the enforcement was set and who/which entity is responsible for the supervision and controlling of its compliance [text]

27. How is the Intervention/Policy/Strategy funded? *

- (a) Public funding

- (b) Private funding
- (c) Both public and private funding
- (d) Other sources of funding
- (e) No funds required
- (f) Don't know

28. Please specify if you answered: (a) Public funding; (b) Private funding; (c) Both public and private funding; or (d) Other sources of funding on Q27: [text]

29. Is the Intervention/Policy/Strategy being monitored? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

30. If yes, who is responsible for the monitoring? [text]

31. If yes, what indicators are used in the monitoring of the process and the outcome of the intervention? [text]

(Indicators are variables measuring the performance of an action and the level to which the set objectives are reached. Process, output, and outcome/impact is ideally reported.)

32. Can you identify any barriers/obstacles to the implementation of the specific Intervention/Policy/Strategy? *

- Yes
- No obstacle/barriers identified so far
- Don't know

33. If you answered Yes on Q32, are the barriers/obstacles related to cost/financing constraints? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

34. If yes, please specify: [text]

35. If you answered Yes on Q32, are the barriers/obstacles related to social/cultural constraints? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

36. If yes, please specify: [text]

37. If you answered Yes on Q32, are the barriers/obstacles related to the degree of acceptability of the Intervention/Policy/Strategy? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

38. If yes, please specify: [text]

39. If you answered Yes on Q32, are the barriers/obstacles related with other implementation barriers? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

40. If yes, please specify: [text]

(Please briefly describe the other barriers/obstacles and how these would influence the implementation of the current intervention/policy/strategy. You can consider the domains and related barriers included in the Table)

Table. Summary of main barriers of current intervention policies related to childhood obesity by different implementation domains

<i>Individual domain</i>
Non-modifiable biology (e.g., genes)
Race or ethnicity
Gender
Early life risks (e.g., infant feeding)
Psychological health
Self-efficacy, body image
Knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs with regard to weight-related behaviors
<i>Family and peers domain</i>
Family socioeconomic position & structure (e.g., single parent)
Family beliefs, sociocultural perceptions of health (physical activity, eating habits, etc.)
Gender
Weight stigma or bullying
Family food preferences

Family psychological stress
Peer support for a healthy lifestyle
<i>Childcare and school domain</i>
Physical activity programs barriers
Educational nutrition programs drawbacks
Foods offered at the school environment and access (i.e., lunch room, vending machines)
Family engagement in school
School related stigma & bullying
<i>Community & Built environment domain</i>
Walkable neighborhoods/access to safe spaces for play/leisure
Fast food restaurants/other establishments selling unhealthy foods and beverages (i.e., convenience stores, etc.)
Food marketing exposure
Accessible primary health care
Availability of healthy and affordable food in the local market
<i>Society domain</i>
Media influences on food market
Cultural forms around weight status, food & physical activity
Race and ethnicity including culturally diverse sub-groups
Media portrayals of weight and beauty
<i>Public policy domain</i>
Local, national, and regional public policies on and investment in: agriculture, food, transport, food industry/marketing, media influence

41. If you have identified barriers/obstacles in the implementation of the specific Intervention/Policy/Strategy, can you identify any opportunities/actions that will help to overcome them facilitating its implementation? *

- Yes
- No

- Don't know

42. If yes, please briefly describe how these opportunities/actions could help to overcome barriers/obstacles for the successful implementation of the specific Intervention/Policy/Strategy. [text]

43. Source of information where the Intervention/Policy/Strategy is described:

(Please provide a reference to a published document and/or a link to a website and/or information for any available documents e.g. reports, articles)

44. In your country, can you identify any OTHER interventions/policies/strategies in relation to the prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence? *

- Yes (Please submit your answers and fill in a new questionnaire)
- No

Thank you for completing the survey!

Appendix 2. Short survey Questionnaire to WP2 PREVENT partners

PREVENT - Questionnaire to identify limitations, barriers, and opportunities in the implementation of interventions, policies, and strategies for the prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence

Information Sheet

PREVENT is a collaborative EU-funded Action to Improve and Upscale Primary Prevention of Cancer by Addressing Childhood Obesity. Through diligent implementation research and a comprehensive approach, PREVENT aims to lay the foundation for a future where healthier lifestyles and brighter tomorrows await every child. It is supported and funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe program. More info can be found on our website: <https://preventproject.eu/>.

The purpose of this questionnaire, which was developed by the National Public Health Organization of Greece, a PREVENT partner, in the context of Task 2.2 of WP2, is to gather information from the WP2 partners on limitations, barriers or obstacles as well as opportunities that have been observed during the implementation of interventions/policies/strategies in relation to the primary prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence.

Your participation will contribute to our project's delivery of the initial PREVENT multi-actor and context aware primary interventions. This is an anonymous questionnaire.

Questions marked with an "*" are mandatory.

We focus on primary prevention of obesity and the age range 9-16 years of age. Please limit the responses for open-ended questions to a maximum of 5 -10 sentences.

1. Can you identify any barriers/obstacles to the implementation of Interventions/Policies/Strategies in relation to the primary prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence? *

- Yes
- No obstacle/barriers identified so far
- Don't know

2. If you answered Yes on Q1, are the barriers/obstacles related to cost/financing constraints? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

3. If yes, please specify: [text]

3. If you answered Yes on Q1, are the barriers/obstacles related to social/cultural constraints? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

4. If yes, please specify: [text]

6. If you answered Yes on Q1, are the barriers/obstacles related to the degree of acceptability of the Interventions/Policies/Strategies? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

7. If yes, please specify: [text]

8. If you answered Yes on Q1, are the barriers/obstacles related with other implementation barriers? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

9. If yes, please specify: [text]

(Please briefly describe the other barriers/obstacles and how these would influence the implementation of the current interventions/policies/strategies. You can consider the domains and related barriers included in the Table)

Table. Summary of main barriers of current intervention policies related to childhood obesity by different implementation domains

<i>Individual domain</i>
Non-modifiable biology (e.g., genes)
Race or ethnicity
Gender
Early life risks (e.g., infant feeding)
Psychological health
Self-efficacy, body image
Knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs with regard to weight-related behaviors
<i>Family and peers domain</i>
Family socioeconomic position & structure (e.g., single parent)

Family beliefs, sociocultural perceptions of health (physical activity, eating habits, etc.)
Gender
Weight stigma or bullying
Family food preferences
Family psychological stress
Peer support for a healthy lifestyle
<i>Childcare and school domain</i>
Physical activity programs barriers
Educational nutrition programs drawbacks
Foods offered at the school environment and access (i.e., lunch room, vending machines)
Family engagement in school
School related stigma & bullying
<i>Community & Built environment domain</i>
Walkable neighborhoods/access to safe spaces for play/leisure
Fast food restaurants/other establishments selling unhealthy foods and beverages (i.e., convenience stores, etc.)
Food marketing exposure
Accessible primary health care
Availability of healthy and affordable food in the local market
<i>Society domain</i>
Media influences on food market
Cultural forms around weight status, food & physical activity
Race and ethnicity including culturally diverse sub-groups
Media portrayals of weight and beauty
<i>Public policy domain</i>
Local, national, and regional public policies on and investment in: agriculture, food, transport, food industry/marketing, media influence

10. If you have identified barriers/obstacles in the implementation of Interventions/Policies/Strategies in relation to the primary prevention of obesity during childhood and adolescence, can you identify any opportunities/actions that will help to overcome them facilitating their implementation? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

11. If yes, please briefly describe how these opportunities/actions could help to overcome barriers/obstacles for the successful implementation of Interventions/Policies/Strategies.

[text]

12. Source of useful information related to the above: *(Please provide a reference to a published document and/or a link to a website and/or information for any available documents e.g. reports, articles)*

Thank you for completing the survey!

Appendix 3. Greece-specific report of the survey results

Type (intervention/policy/strategy) and content

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents' guidelines form a national **policy**. The guidelines constitute an essential nutrition policy tool used to inform and educate the general population about healthy dietary habits and regular physical activity for infants, children, and adolescents with the ultimate goal to protect and promote their health. The guidelines are evidence-based and are provided in the form of frequency and amount of consumption of main food groups. Healthy tips for meal consumption, preparation and preservation and behavioral advice to establish and promote healthy dietary habits and behaviors in children and adolescents are also provided.

2-School Canteen Standards

The School Canteens Standards (with an official catalogue of food-products approved for sale at the Greek school canteens) are mandatory for all school canteens in private and public schools in Greece. They are considered a **policy**. The Standards were developed in 2013 by the National Nutrition Policy Committee based in previous standards and were adopted from the Greek Ministry of Health. Their main objective is to promote healthy eating and healthy food choices during school hours, as well as protect student's health from the regular consumption of food-products considered unhealthy.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The WHO Child Growth Standards were endorsed as national growth standards in 2017 substituting previous national growth standards. They are considered a **policy**. The standards are used for recording and monitoring physical growth and development of Greek infants, children and adolescents and they are embedded in the Personal Child Record of each child born in Greece. The main objective of the growth standards is to determine whether a child is growing "normally" or has a growth problem or trend towards a growth problem that should be addressed.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

This can be considered an **intervention** program. It involves educational material that was developed and launched in 2019 by the Hellenic Dietetics Association with the aim to educate children and raise their awareness in relation to the importance of healthy and balanced dietary habits. The material was approved by the Ministry of Health and the Institute of Educational Policy of the Ministry of Education. The material is available for the teachers to be used as part of the Health Education in schools. The implementation of the education is optional and depends on the teacher that will be responsible for its implementation.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

The Scheme introduces best practices in schools aiming to increase awareness for vegetables, fruits, and milk. The Scheme, which can be characterized as **an intervention program**, was launched in Greece during 2009-2010 school year and merged with the EU School Milk Scheme on 1 August 2017 into one legal framework based on the Regulation on the new School Fruit, Vegetables and Milk Scheme (Regulation EU No 2016/791). The scheme is funded through the EU's common agricultural policy and supports the distribution of fruit, vegetables, and milk products to schools across the EU as part of a wider programme of education about European agriculture and the benefits of healthy eating. It provides financing to Member States based on the number of school children and level of development of the country. The implementation of the programmes is at the discretion of national or regional governments, but to receive funding, they must distribute fruit, vegetables and milk products in schools and implement educational measures, such as farm and market visits, educational material distributed to teachers and interactive games on education and nutrition, and regularly monitor and evaluate implementation. Foods containing added sugars, salt, fat, sweeteners, or artificial flavor enhancers are exempt from the scheme: as an exception, limited quantities of added sugar, salt and fat are allowed if they are approved by the Member States' health/nutrition authorities. The Member States determine the frequency and duration of the distribution of the food.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

A public information campaign on healthy nutrition and dietary habits has been implemented periodically on a national level in order to increase awareness of the general population on healthy nutrition issues. This campaign is part of the Greek national nutrition policy, and it can be considered an **intervention** action.

Health outcome targeted

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The guidelines do not aim for a specific health outcome/s but for overall optimal health and development, prevention of nutritional deficiencies, maintenance of normal weight and prevention of obesity and chronic diseases later in life.

2-School Canteen Standards

There is no specific health outcome targeted. The general aim is to prevent obesity and chronic diet-related diseases later in life.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The outcomes of the child growth standards are the indices who reflect growth and development. Specific anthropometric indices are measured such as body weight, body length or height, head circumference and body mass index.

4-Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

There is no specific health outcome targeted although the aim of the health promotion education is the promotion of good health, prevention of obesity and chronic diseases in later life.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

The is no specific health outcome targeted, but overall health and well-being of the children is promoted.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

The is no specific health outcome targeted, but overall health and well-being, as well as the reduction of nutrition related chronic diseases for the whole population.

Scale/context (school, family, etc.), Level (national, regional, local) and Setting of implementation (public or private or both)

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The national food-based dietary guidelines are implemented in schools, child-care settings, families, and communities, as well as in the whole society. The level of implementation is national and the setting both public and private sector.

2-School Canteen Standards

The policy is implemented in public and private schools at the national level.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The Growth Standards are implemented in the public and private health sector at the national level.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

This educational program is implemented at schools, private and public, at the national level.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

This intervention is implemented at schools, in the public sector and at national level.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

The campaign is implemented at the whole society (school, family, community, such as civic centers, recreation centers, scouts, etc.), clinical setting (e.g., primary care health centers, outpatient Clinics, etc.), mass media, municipal markets, etc.), sports facilities, in the public and private sector at national level.

Target populations and target stakeholders

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The guidelines are targeting individuals from birth until 18 years old. The involved stakeholders for the implementation of the policy are many. More specifically: the parents and caregivers, all health professionals and pediatricians, nutritionists, people responsible for the school

canteens and schools' meals, school principals, teachers and professors, policy makers of the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education.

2-School Canteen Standards

The Standards target elementary school, high school, and lyceum students, that is children and adolescents 6-17 years of age. The relevant stakeholders are individuals responsible for managing the school canteens, the school administration, the teachers and professors, the students, the public health policy makers, the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education, the food industry, and business related to marketing of food-product to kids.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The growth standards refer to individuals from birth until 18 years old. The related stakeholders for the implementation of the growth standards in practice are pediatricians and primary care physicians. The Ministry of Health and the national Institute of Child's Health are responsible for the endorsement and dissemination of information to pediatricians and the public and the Universities for the education and training of health professionals.

4-Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

These programs refer to children in secondary school (Gymnasium and Lykeion) from 12-18 years old. The target stakeholders are professors, students, school administration, the Ministry of Health, and the Ministry of Education.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

The program is targeting students attending Primary Education (children aged 6-12) school units in selected regions of the country, as defined in the relevant proclamations, and determined by the Ministries of Rural Development and Food and Education, Religion and Sports.), parents, teachers and headteachers of the educational establishments.

The related stakeholders are the Ministry of Rural Development and Food, the Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs and the Ministry of Health, the Greek Payment Authority of Common Agricultural Policy (C.A.P.) Aid Schemes, and the General Directorate of Regional Agricultural Economy & Veterinary Medicine. School principals and teachers are also included in the related stakeholders.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

The campaign is targeting the whole population (children, teenagers, and adults). The relevant stakeholders are the parents and caregivers, all health professionals, nutritionists, school principals, teachers and professors, policy makers of the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education.

Place and duration of the implementation

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The guidelines are implemented throughout Greece and they are currently in effect until its update (the guidelines were launched in 2014).

2-School Canteen Standards

The Standards are implemented throughout Greece, and they are currently in effect until its update (the standards were launched in 2013).

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The growth standards are implemented throughout Greece, and they are currently in effect until its update (the standards were endorsed in 2017).

4-Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

This is educational material was developed and launched in 2019 and endorsed by the Ministry of Health. The program is still ongoing.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

This scheme is implemented in primary education school units in selected regions of the country. The program is ongoing.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

The campaign is implemented throughout Greece, focusing on schools, families, community clinical settings. The campaign started in 2013 with a duration of 10 years.

Type of material/tools used for the implementation/Digital tools used

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The guidelines are available in the form of printed and electronic files for the general public and health professionals. More specifically, the Ministry of Health provides printed and online material (e.g. posters, pamphlets, and the actual guides for the public) with guidelines addressing the parents, the caregivers, the teachers as well as older kids. Also, material with the scientific rational and evidence supporting the guidelines has been developed for health professionals and is available online. The guidelines are also available from the Ministries of Health and Education for the teachers and professors in order to use them in class for health promotion purposes. The guides, brochures, and posters for the parents/caregivers and for health professionals are available to download or read through a special site.

2-School Canteen Standards

There are no specific tools used for the implementation of the Standards.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The growth charts are incorporated in the Child's Health Record Booklet that each child has in order to record information related to child's health, monitoring of growth and development, immunization records, screening tests, other preventive examinations, therapies and every potential health issue. A special tool to implement the growth chart measurements is available for the pediatricians.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

For the implementation of the specific education program a power point presentation for the teachers is available. The implementation of the program is optional and depends on the teacher's decision to implement the specific program or not at school.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

Besides the distribution of products (fruits, vegetables, and milk), the program includes the implementation of educational measures, as well as promotion and evaluation measures. The educational measures of the Program include the implementation of a healthy nutrition program by the teachers of the country's Primary Education units, which is addressed to the students. **Digital tools** have been implemented such as an online platform with specific thematic sections (<https://trefomastesosta.gr>), a teacher's guide, and multimodal/interactive educational material. Materials include course presentations, unit consolidation/assessment activities, games and printables. The platform also includes relevant informational material for parents and guardians.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

The campaign used mainly printed material such as posters and leaflets, which were distributed to the general public and in various settings. Publications to general newspapers, educational speeches to the public, and schools etc. were implemented in order to disseminate the guidelines for healthy nutrition as well as the role of adhering to traditional Mediterranean diet. The material could be downloaded from the internet.

Use of behavioral models and participatory methods

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

No behavioral model has been applied for the development of these guidelines.

2-School Canteen Standards

No behavioral model has been applied for the development of these standards.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

No behavioral model has been applied for the development of these standards.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

No behavioral model has been applied for the development of these programs.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

No behavioral model has been applied for the development of this scheme.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

No behavioral model has been applied for the development of the campaign.

Support by a legal framework, enforcement methods and funds

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

The Ministry of Health sends regularly ministerial circulars that remind about the existence of national dietary guidelines and their implementation. Furthermore, there is no specific enforcement law. The development of the Guidelines was supported by funds of the Greek government and EU funds.

2-School Canteen Standards

The Standards were included in a ministerial order published in an official government gazette (since 2013). There is regular monitoring of adherence with the Standards and the product catalogue by the employees of the government responsible for the preservation of good hygiene in the premises serving food and beverages. Moreover, the products sold in the canteens are monitored and fines are given if the Standards are not followed. There is public funding available if needed for the school canteen standards.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

Yes, growth standards were officially supported by the Ministry of Health. There is no enforcement procedure and no funding required.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

There is no support from a legal framework nor enforcement procedure. The program had no funding.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

There are specific regulations that have been issued for this scheme:

- Regulation (EU) No. 1308/2013 of the European Parliament and European Council (EE L 347 της 20-12-2013, p. 671),
- Regulation (EU) No. 2017/39 of the European Commission (EE L 5 της 10-01-2017, p. 1)
- Regulation (EU) No. 2017/40 of the European Commission (EE L 5 της 10-01-2017, p. 11)
- European Commission Regulation (EU) No. 2022/245 of 13 December 2021 amending the delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/40 as regards accompanying training measures and the selection and approval of aid applicants
- Joint Ministerial Decision no. 1/1135/04-01-2021 (ΦΕΚ 5/Β´/4-1-2021) Joint Ministerial Decision as amended by Joint Ministerial Decision no. 1126/230060/1-9-2021 (ΦΕΚ 4023/ Β´ /1-9-2021).

There is enforcement of the regulation and a specific funding from EU and national funds.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

There is no support from a legal framework nor enforcement procedure. The program development was supported by public funding.

Monitoring

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

There is not a monitoring mechanism of adherence to the guidelines in place.

2-School Canteen Standards

The Standards are being monitored by public agencies in terms of the products allowed to be sold in the canteens.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

There is not a monitoring mechanism in place.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

There is not a monitoring mechanism of adherence to the education programs in place.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

The scheme is being monitored by: (a) the Ministry of Rural Development and Food; and (b) the Greek Payment Authority of Common Agriculture Policy Aid Schemes (OPEKEPE). The programme is being evaluated in accordance with Article 8(2) of Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 2017/39 and Article 9(2) and (5) of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 2017/40 on the basis of the following criteria: (A) the rate of increase in the consumption of fruit/vegetables and milk by primary school children; (B) how effectively the implemented programme functioned; (C) the various parameters of the programme which affected its effectiveness, efficiency and relevance. The target group which will be used for the evaluation of the programme are children aged 6-12, parents, teachers and headteachers of the educational establishments. The rate of increase in the consumption of fruit/vegetables and milk after the programme is implemented will be measured on the basis of a study of the initial situation/measurement at the end of the implementation of the programme. Specifically, two measurements will be taken per year, one before the products are distributed (Initial Measurement) and a second (Final Measurement) as close as possible to the end of the programme in each participating educational establishment (during the final weeks of distribution of the products). The above evaluation under point (A), the evaluation of whether the implemented programme functioned effectively (B) and which parameters influenced the effectiveness, efficiency and relevance of the programme (C) will be awarded following a tender procedure to a specific external contractor on the basis of guidelines included in the call for tender.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

No monitoring was implemented.

Barriers

1-National Food-based Dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

Several barriers have been identified by the CoP:

a) Barriers related to the cost: The wider dissemination and continuity of educational programs and related activities promoting the implementation of the dietary guidelines by the general population is impaired by lack of funding. Lack of digital assistive tools was also impaired by lack of funding.

b) Barriers related to social/cultural issues: People with different dietary habits due to different cultural background may not adhere to the guidelines. Vulnerable populations with low SES may not have adequate access to the guidelines and may not understand them.

Other types of implementation barriers reported:

i) There was an initial wide dissemination of the guidelines to the general public, but no continuity of this dissemination was established.

ii) The guidelines did not reach many related to nutrition health professionals.

iii) The guidelines were available from the Hellenic Institution of Educational policies, but there is no information about their actual dissemination to the schools.

iv) A more systematic integration of the guidelines with the implementation of nutrition education program at the schools as well as the food served in the canteens was not achieved.

v) There was no study to evaluate the effectiveness of the national guidelines in terms of achieving their final goal, such as adherence to healthier dietary habits, or change towards healthier nutritional choices.

2-School Canteen Standards

Several barriers in the successful implementation of the Standards were identified:

a) Barriers related to the cost: No funds are available for the regular information of students and parents about the products that should be sold in the canteens and their connection with health and well-being.

b) Barriers related to acceptability: The healthy options offered by the canteens are not so popular among students.

Other types of implementation barriers reported:

i) The school administration uses the money earned from renting the canteens as an income to reinforce their budget. Thus, profit is their main consideration and adherence to the Standards.

ii) Monitoring of adherence to the Standards by the relevant public employers is inadequate and not effective.

iii) There is room for more connection of the products with the promotion of healthy diet and nutrition education at school.

3-WHO Child Growth Standards - National growth standards

The main barrier reported was that a wider and better implementation of the growth charts is required. Furthermore, not enough information is provided to the parents and the general public in order to understand their importance and the importance of monitoring growth and development.

4- Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

The main barriers reported referred to their optional use by the teachers and professors, the content of the material, which was not very interesting for the students, as well as there was no study to provide evidence for its effectiveness in terms of behavioral change.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

Results from evaluation reports related to the scheme implemented in Greece for the years 2017/2018 until 2020/2021, showed that not enough national funds were available for this scheme as well as several organizational delays were reported in the initiation of the project.

Also, another national evaluation report for the period 2017-2022 showed that students had positively received the project and more than 80% of the parents evaluated the project as good or very good. Almost 70% of the parents reported that kids did not drink the milk at the school and returned it back to school, something that was worrying in terms of food safety.

Several issues related to the collaboration between the schools and the government ministerial department in charge of the implementation of the scheme were also reported.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

Barriers related to the lack of funding which impaired the wide implementation of the campaign as well as its sustainability, lack of cultural adaptation, and the need of additional communication channels required were reported.

Areas of opportunities/ Opportunities for improvement

1-National food-based dietary guidelines for infants, children, and adolescents

An area of opportunity for the National Food-based Dietary Guidelines is the use of digital means in order to better engage end-users and to monitor the acceptability level of the implementation. Moreover, more funding is considered necessary to disseminate widely the guidelines and integrate them in the educational system, reaching the students, the parents, the general public and the health professionals.

2-School canteen standards

The School Canteen Standards policy needs more opportunities for informing the students and their parents about the importance of a healthy snack. In addition, more nutrition education initiatives would be helpful in promoting healthy eating. Also, another area for improvement is to take actions to strengthen the monitoring of the implementation of the Standards. Last but not least, the profit earned from the rent of the canteen should be disconnected from the products sold by the canteen.

3-WHO Child growth standards - national growth standards

Improving the dissemination of information regarding the significance of growth charts is crucial for enhancing the National Growth Standards policy.

4-Health promotion education programs for students in secondary schools– Nutrition education

Utilizing digital tools will enrich the Health Promotion Education Program, facilitating the conveyance of messages and expanding its reach. Enhancing the presentation is essential for effectively announcing the program. Furthermore, strengthening engagement from families and the wider school community is a critical aspect that needs improvement.

5- The EU School fruit, vegetables, and milk scheme

Two primary areas for improvement are evident in the aforementioned policy. Firstly, there's a need for ensuring the prompt initiation and smooth operation of the program. To achieve this, procedures related to the preparation and execution of electronic tenders, as well as those for project and study assignments (such as selecting contractors for publicity projects, overseeing educational measures, evaluating projects, and choosing suppliers for fruits, vegetables, and milk), must be expedited.

Secondly, it's imperative that the call for interest by the Ministry of Education and Culture reaches all school units nationwide interested in joining the Program within the next three years. Furthermore, it's suggested that the selection of participating school units be handled by the competent Regional Directorates of Education based on socio-economic criteria, ensuring compliance with the maximum student capacity set by the Ministry of Education and Culture.

6- Public information campaign on nutrition

To further improve this campaign, it's essential to link media representations and social media with the concept of health (associated with a normal weight) and beauty, promoting the idea of a healthy body achieved through reduced consumption of junk food. Achieving this goal will require a more extensive campaign effort.

Appendix 4. Spain (Catalonia)-specific report of the survey results

Type (intervention/policy/strategy) and content

1-The Daily Mile

The Daily Mile is an **intervention** focused on promoting social physical activity that takes place outside during the school day at a time of the teacher's choosing, with the objective of improving physical, social, emotional, and mental health and wellbeing of the children – regardless of age, ability or personal circumstances.

The aim is for children to run, jog or wheel for 15 minutes in the fresh air with friends, in their school clothes - no equipment required. However, children can also walk at their own pace if necessary, or if they need to catch their breath.

2-Active Pauses

The **intervention** Active Pauses is characterized by short periods of physical activity, which last between 5 and 10 minutes and take place within the classroom.

The activity aims to reduce the time of inactivity of students during school hours, develop a positive attitude toward physical activity and increase daily energy expenditure in physical activity. To facilitate its implementation, the intervention is designed to work on curricular content, in a limited space like the classroom, and can be done any time during the day.

3-School Menus Review Programme: More Healthy and Sustainable School Canteens (PreME-MEMSS)

The PreME-MEMSS is an **intervention** that evaluates the menus of pre-school, primary and secondary schools that have a canteen service, and promotes changes in their menu planning to promote healthier and more sustainable food. It also aims to know the acceptance of the meals served in order to increase their nutritional quality and initiate strategies that lead to reduce food waste; therefore, it aims to care for the health of people, territories and the planet at the same time.

After the evaluation, PreME-MEMSS offers training, advice, and support to educational centres so they can identify and implement improvements and promotes changes in the management model that deals with structural aspects of food acquisition and kitchen management (e.g., equipment, kitchen staff or budget of food menus). At the same time, it helps design school menus that are rich in plant-based proteins, whole grain products, olive oil and fresh fruits and limit the consumption of sugar, highly processed products, and red meat. Moreover, it encourages the consumption of local and seasonal products to raise awareness of the need to strengthen our local economy and farming and contribute to the good health of our ecosystems.

The program has different phases:

- **Phase 1:** Registration, Start of the course, First informative session

- **Phase 2:** Preliminary analysis, Initial Questionnaire Diagnostic Report, Training of the four groups involved
- **Phase 3:** Design of the action plan, Preparation of the action plan
- **Phase 4:** Implementing the changes, Implementation Monographic training
- **Phase 5:** Final evaluation, continuation, End of course, Assessment

4-Prevention and management of childhood obesity in the neighbourhood La Mina (La Mina)

This is a **primary health care centre and community-based intervention** that was piloted in a vulnerable high priority neighbourhood. The model of prevention and care for childhood obesity is based on a multidisciplinary and multilevel approach to the individual aspects and the environment of the child and the family, with the aim of acting on: nutrition, physical activity and exercise, sedentary lifestyle and screen time, leisure, hours of sleep and positive and respectful parenting, taking into account social determinants.

The main objectives are:

- To improve the habits of children with obesity and reduce the prevalence of excess weight through a comprehensive approach to health.
- Improve the capacity of professional teams in primary health care, in the prevention and addressing of obesity.
- Homogenize the intervention of other professionals and support devices.
- Guarantee continuity of care between levels and professionals.
- Reduce the variability of prevention and care for childhood obesity and reduce the effects of social inequalities on it.

5-INFADIMED

INFADIMED is an **intervention** based on primary health care and we promote the Mediterranean diet as a healthy lifestyle for students aged 3 to 12 with **interventions in schools and the community**. Nurses trained in the intervention provide healthy lifestyle education at schools and community centers with interactive education materials including a series of cartoons. It is currently piloting a streaming platform to bring content to families via mobile devices.

There are 5 interventions per course, each intervention lasting 45 minutes. They are distributed during the school year: one or two in the first term, two in the second term and one or two in the second term. The program evolves as the students grow. The first season is in 13, and the last in 6th grade. In total, there are 9 years of the program where different topics related to each other are worked on throughout the years.

The main objectives: Prevention of non-communicable diseases by improving children's healthy habits. Decrease the prevalence and incidence of childhood obesity and promote an active life.

6-SEEDS (Science Engagement to Empower Disadvantaged Adolescents)

SEEDS is an **intervention** funded by the European Union. The intervention is based on extreme citizen science, and adolescents from Greece, UK, the Netherlands and Spain with leadership characteristics are named ambassadors and co-create interventions for the improvement of

lifestyles and increase STEM interest of their peers. Each country will select 15 teenagers from intervention schools called ambassadors, who will participate throughout the project. In each country, focus groups with ambassadors and stakeholders will focus on physical activity, snacking behavior and STEM. Input from the focus groups will be used to shape Makeathon events, co-creation events where teens and stakeholders develop interventions. The resulting intervention will be implemented in the intervention schools for 6 months.

SEEDS is designed to tackle both challenges, (a) promoting healthier lifestyles and (b) increasing STEM interest among adolescents from deprived areas. This multi-country project aims to listen to adolescents living in deprived areas and to empower them to make a change towards a healthy and active lifestyle.

7-SEISMO

A randomized controlled trial of a School-based health Education **Intervention** to Stimulate the resilience and Motivation for preventing pediatric Obesity among vulnerable populations. SEÍSMO (acronym of School Physical Education Intervention to Stimulate the intrinsic Motivation for Preventing Pediatric Obesity) is a project that seeks to make the subject of Physical Education the epicenter of a healthy earthquake which expands into tutorships and all educational spaces in the school by involving the entire educational community, providing teachers with tools and materials to integrate healthy habits in the school.

The main objective is to encourage the physical, psychological, and social development of children aged 6–12 through the promotion of healthy habits and abilities for life, bringing about distinct acts in the school environment and implying all levels of the educational community-the students, their families, and teachers.

Health outcome targeted

1-The Daily Mile

The Daily Mile helps children be more active and less sedentary and significantly improves both their attitudes towards physical activity and their **fitness levels**. Consequently, it improves their bone health, muscle strength, and heart health, and it reduces body fat and promotes healthy body composition.

The activity also improves children's **social and emotional wellbeing**; children report feeling happier, more awake and calmer after doing The Daily Mile, and teachers report after the activity children work better together and improve their peer-to-peer and teacher-child relationships. As the activity supports their self-esteem, confidence, and happiness, and helps reduce anxiety, classroom behaviour improves as a result.

The Daily Mile also has a positive impact on **children's academic performance**: their attention, focus and concentration improve, as well as their memory function, problem solving, alertness and overall ability to learn.

2-Active Pauses

During the implementation of Active Pauses:

- The number of participants' physical activity during school hours increased by 50%.
- 75.8% of the students felt more active.
- 58.5% more **motivated**.

- 51% showed a **better attitude** after the activities.
- 87.5% of teachers considered possible the daily implementation of the activity.

3-PreME-MEMSS

The compliance with PreME-MEMSS's recommendations in the meals provided by school cafeterias, can contribute to improving children's diet, and healthy eating in childhood can promote **optimal growth and development, better learning, and improved health and well-being.**

4-La Mina

Adherence level of families/children, number of professionals participating in trainings, stakeholder entities, number of and participation in community activities.

Assessment of semi-structured interviews of: **frequency of food consumption** (including sugary drinks, fast food), 24-hour dietary reminders, **routine health variables, screen use, physical activity**, recording and monitoring of food records query and the general assessment of the variables "∞|9 5 2 1 0" (including **emotional health and adequate sleep**)

Well-being at school (if it works well and it pleases them) and school performance

Anthropometric measurements

Level of satisfaction (children and families, health professional training and community activities)

5-INFADIMED

Number of schools participating in the program, number of **participating students** per school, **survey results**, monitoring and evaluation of participants' **anthropometric data** through the ECAP program. Tools: Program evaluation surveys, Mediterranean Diet Adherence Survey (KIDMED), International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), emotional well-being KIDSCREEN.

6-SEEDS

Healthy lifestyles and STEM interest. To evaluate and compare if students adopted healthy lifestyles and if STEM outcomes have changed, all adolescents from intervention and control schools will complete questionnaires related to healthy and active living and STEM outcomes at baseline (before Makeathons in November 2021) and at follow-up (June2022). The questionnaires include parts of validated and non-validated questionnaires.

Primary outcomes as Lifestyle-related outcomes: **physical activity, snacking behaviour, and STEM outcomes** (interest in life science, science capital, and interest in STEM career pathways).

Outcomes of the Makeathons will define the themes of interventions and concepts, the number of associated activities, and how the activities should be disseminated and implemented. Makeathons are considered as part of the intervention as adolescents actively participate in this event.

7-SEISMO

The target outcomes are **BMI z-score, Waist-to-height ratio**

Incidence of overweight, obesity, severe obesity, and abdominal obesity

Quality of life

Lifestyles: Dietary pattern/Physical Activity/ Use of screens/ Sleep duration and quality/Psychological well-being

Psychosocial factors related to health behaviours such as attitudes, social influence, self-efficacy, skills, and barriers.

Scale/context (school, family, etc), Level (national, regional, local) and Setting of implementation (Public or private or both)

1-The Daily Mile

The intervention is implemented at a **national level** and has already been implemented in 38 public and public-private **schools** of Catalonia.

2-Active Pauses

There hasn't been a pilot study done in Catalonia yet, but the activity is planned to be implemented in **schools** in Catalonia in **both public and private settings**.

3-PreME-MEMSS

The intervention is implemented at a **regional level**, and it focuses on **both public and private settings**. The context of implementation are **primary or secondary schools** in Catalonia that have a canteen service.

4-La Mina

The intervention is implemented at a **local level and is planned to be scaled up to the regional level**, focussing on primary health centre catchment areas that have the highest rates of childhood obesity. The context is aimed at families, primary health care centres, schools, the community, with a broader scope of the whole society as well as public policy. The two main settings consisted of the neighbourhood primary health care centre (Public) as well as community actions (public and private).

5-INFADIMED

It is implemented at the **regional level** in nursery and primary schools, community centres and municipal markets. Currently, 225 schools throughout Catalonia participate in the program, being both public and private entities.

6-SEEDS

The level of implementation is at the **European level**, within the context of school settings and is publically funded.

7-SEISMO

The intervention is implemented **nationally** in publicly funded primary education schools.

Target populations and target stakeholders

1-The Daily Mile

The target population are **children aged 6-12 years** (primary school), and the target stakeholder is the **Public Health Agency of Catalonia**.

2-Active Pauses

The target population are **children aged 3-12** (kindergarten and primary school) and the target stakeholder is the **Public Health Agency of Catalonia**.

3-PreME-MEMSS

The target population are **children that have lunch at their primary or secondary school's cafeteria**. The agents involved are the management team of the school, catering companies, chefs, monitoring companies, the associations of student families and local authorities.

The main stakeholders are the **Catalan Public Health Agency (ASPCAT)** and **Barcelona Public Health Agency (ASPB)** - Municipality Section of Urban Food Policies and Barcelona Education Consortium.

4-La Mina

The target population includes **all children, youth and their families** living in the intervention **neighbourhood La Mina**, so as to promote healthy lifestyles as well as **children between 2 and 14 years of age with obesity (and their families)** derived from primary health care paediatric services and who resided in La Mina.

Stakeholders include: The entities that work with children in the neighbourhood (schools, playgrounds, play centers, libraries, civic centers, sports clubs/associations, etc.), health services, City Hall, Catalan Public Health Agency, Food suppliers/stores, associated entities, etc.

5-INFADIMED

The target population are **children aged 3 to 13 years and their families**. Stakeholders include **healthcare, educational and community entities**.

6-SEEDS

The target population are **adolescents aged 13 to 15 years**. Target stakeholders: The SEEDS project is rooted in the Quadruple Helix model including four sectors: **government, community, business, and academia**.

7-SEISMO

The target populations are **children aged 6 to 12 years old and their families**. Target stakeholders are **teachers and the entire educational community**.

Place and duration of the implementation

1-The Daily Mile

The intervention is being implemented in **Catalonia**; it started on August 2022, and it will be implemented for **3 years**.

2-Active Pauses

The intervention will be implemented in **Catalonia**, it is undergoing the process of review and authorisation.

3-PreME-MEMSS

The intervention is being implemented **regionally**; the revision of the menus started on 2006, and the pilot evaluation of the "Healthier and more sustainable school canteens" started during the 2020-2021 school year. The number of public pre-school and primary schools that participated in this pilot test was 6, and a total of 1,655 children were involved.

4-La Mina

The intervention was conducted in the **neighbourhood La Mina, located in the city of Barcelona**, Catalonia. In July 2019 the Primary Health Care team training and meetings with neighbourhood entities were initiated. The Primary health care intervention took place between February 2021 – December 2022. Although the project began in July 2019, the arrival of the pandemic halted the intervention activities until its restart in February 2021.

5-INFADIMED

Nursery and primary schools, community, and municipal markets. The intervention was piloted from 2011 to 2015. It was expanded between 2019 and 2020 and is currently being implemented in schools throughout **Catalonia**.

6-SEEDS

The implementation took place in **high schools from deprived areas in four European countries** (Greece, United Kingdom, Netherlands, and Spain). It began in 2021 and will last 5 years.

7-SEISMO

The intervention started in 2020 and will last 6 years. It's being implemented in **primary schools throughout Spain**. Although the schools are publicly funded, the intervention also counts in part on private economic support that enables reaching other schools located in other municipalities.

Type of material/tools used for the implementation/Digital tools used

1-The Daily Mile

The materials used are:

- Information collected on the web page of the Public Health Agency of Catalonia (https://salutpublica.gencat.cat/ca/ambits/promocio_salut/activitat_fisica/Centres-educatius/index.html)
- One informational webinar in collaboration with the Education Department.
- Promotion of the program with newsletters.
- One Webinar with participating schools to get feedback.

2-Active Pauses

For now, the materials used are information collected on the Public Health Agency of Catalonia and promoting the program with different newsletters.

3-PreME-MEMSS

For the reviewing stage, the materials are the following:

1. **Menu review instructions:** weekly and monthly frequencies, comments, school menu review sheet
2. **Tables of recommended frequencies of food** (Public Health Agency of Catalonia)
3. **Excel DB**
4. **Individual school reports** (templates)
5. Phase 1 and Phase 2 **questionnaires** (to send to schools)

To support the change of the school menus, we provide the agents of change with key documents, informative materials and guides published by the Catalan Public Health Agency (ASPCAT) within the framework of the program.

Digital materials are also used: an application where the information of the school menu (frequencies, etc.) is entered and which allows you to extract the evaluation report from the menu following the recommended criteria is at the schools' disposal. Also, a new clouded based platform is being developed.

4-La Mina

Tool Box for promoting healthy lifestyles and/or monitoring physical activity as a family, eating challenges, infographics, diary for monitoring commitments or challenge calendars, self-monitoring, workshops.

Existing ASPCAT materials: Small Changes to Eat Better, Healthy eating during school years. Guide for Families and Schools 2020, Councils for Healthy Food at the Institute. Recommendations for young people and families, 10 tricks to be more active (+5 years).

New materials created specifically for the intervention, including recipes for foods that are not widely accepted by children. Behavioural support workshops for improving the relationship with setting limits and managing emotions related to habits they intend to acquire/ healthy eating guidelines adapted to the Stage/moment of change of the family and their economic possibilities. Materials related to the umbrella framework |∞|95210.

Digital tools included emails, online meeting, WhatsApp/cell phones. A specific email was created to facilitate unexpected schedule changes and reduce the difficulties of managing appointments directly with the Primary Health Care Centre. This also facilitated communication with the sending of personalized materials and was a means of monitoring along with phone calls via mobile phone and WhatsApp.

5-INFADIMED

Series of **animated cartoons with interactive print materials**. A **streaming platform** is currently under development to share with families via mobile phones.

<https://www.youtube.com/@infadimed/featured>

6-SEEDS

The materials used for the intervention implementation are different in each country depending on the intervention co-created in each country.

7-SEISMO

The intervention is structured into **three major activity modules**:

- **Physical Education Module (PEM)**: promotion of healthy habits within the physical education class through sports activities led by the previously trained teacher.
- **Family module (FAM)**: involves students' family environment in promoting healthy habits through pedagogical material that families receive at home and promotes the practice of family activities.
- **Healthy spaces module (HSM)**: promotes the improvement and transformation of recreational spaces to give continuity to the health promotion at school in relation with the other modules.

The PEM also includes some educational materials to strengthen the implementation of the guide's activities. This is the list of educational materials that complete the PEM: passport, giant harvard plate (85), Healthy Galaxy collage, implementation support resources, SEÍSMO T-shirt for PETS, and the behavioural contract for families related with HEP, PAP, SDP and PWP.

The FAM is led by TUTs. This includes 6 family home activities, 6 tutoring with the children, 6 motivational messages, 6 video tips about healthy habits for families and 1 healthy closing event.

No digital tools are used.

Use of behavioural models and participatory methods (yes, no, if yes which)

1-The Daily Mile & 2-Active Pauses: Neither of the methods were used.

3-PreME-MEMSS

Behavioural models were not used, but participatory methods were. The review of the school menu is offered every three years in order to cover the maximum number of schools in Catalonia and is structured in 3 phases:

- **Phase 1** (September-January). Initial evaluation of a monthly meal plan and preparation of the report with suggestions for improvement.
- **Phase 2** (March-April). Follow-up of the actions taken by schools after receipt of the initial report. This phase began in 2012 and is offered to all schools that have completed phase 1.
- **Phase 3** (May-June). Sensory assessment by the program's staff of school meals and the cafeteria. This was launched on a pilot basis in 2015 and is carried out in schools that have completed Phases 1 and 2.

Each school year, the assessment of the agents involved (school management, management company, canteen monitors, families) is collected by a questionnaire. With this information, the program is improved from one year to the next, incorporating requests, suggestions, etc.

4-La Mina

Behavioural models applied in the intervention include the Transtheoretical model, Motivational interviewing, and Positive parenting. Participatory methods included the following:

- Group sessions with community leaders/stakeholders to establish a shared diagnosis of the determinants of obesity in the neighbourhood and the resources and assets to confront it.
- Training seminars aimed at Primary Health Care professionals (positive parenting and attention to vulnerable families and the motivational interview).
- Information sessions for professionals and neighbourhood entities (identified by the Primary Health Care Team, EAP).
- Satisfaction surveys for professionals, children, and families
- Focus groups with children on the strategy |∞|95210

5-INFADIMED

Participatory methods: At the end of the school year, the management teams of the schools and the reference nurses of the program reflect on the subjects worked on, the content is reviewed and new health issues of concern to the teaching and health community are proposed. From here, the educational content is adapted to the new needs.

The activities in the community are also agreed upon with the promoters, be it the town hall or the municipal market. At the end, a balance is made of the activity and an analysis of improvements.

6-SEEDS

Behavioural models: The question route of focus groups is based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour.

Participatory methods: To ensure the feasibility and the Citizen Science approach, the results of the focus groups will guide the Makeathons and the intervention phase.

Adolescents participated in focus groups (75 min to define the barriers and necessities), received an online training consists of tutorials and exercises to practice the theoretical aspects about citizen science, healthy lifestyles, and STEM. Then, adolescents participated in the co-creation by a makeathon (event of 2-5 hours). Then these adolescents participated in the dissemination of the results obtained.

7-SEISMO

Behavioural models used: ASE Model, Resilience theory, Transtheoretical model (stages of change) and motivational interviewing.

Participatory methods: Feedback from the educational community, to decide certain contents and rhythms of the intervention and for every school year.

Support by a legal framework, enforcement methods and funds

1-The Daily Mile & 2-Active Pauses

Yes, the Interdepartmental and Intersectoral Public Health Plan (PINSAP) of the Generalitat de Catalunya is an initiative aligned with the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) to promote health from all areas of Government action and society, that is to say "health to all policies".

Also, the aim of the Health Plan 2021-2025 is to promote equal opportunities in health throughout life (for example risk reduction: of physical inactivity, tobacco, and alcohol consumption, maintain or decrease the prevalence of excess weight); healthy environments and integration of health care.

The Public Health Agency of Catalonia is responsible for enforcing the intervention as well as supervising and controlling its compliance, and there are no funds required.

3-PreME-MEMSS

The program is built within the framework of the Comprehensive Plan for the Promotion of Health through Physical Activity and Healthy Eating (PAAS) of the Public Health Agency of Catalonia (ASPCAT), and parallel to the Strategy for Nutrition, Physical Activity and Prevention of Obesity (NAOS Strategy). It is also part of the Barcelona 2030 Healthy and Sustainable Lifestyle Strategy and complies with Law 17/2011 on food safety and nutrition.

The actions are not enforced, and they are publicly funded: economic and technical resources come from the Barcelona Public Health Agency, and material resources (application) from the Public Health Agency of Catalonia.

4-La Mina

The intervention is not supported by a legal framework and thus is not enforced. It is primarily funded by public funding (primary health care centre actions), with the exception of some joint public/private funding for community activities.

5-INFADIMED

The only legal framework is that the intervention has the approval of the IDIAP Jordi Gol Research Ethics Committee

6-SEEDS

Legal framework: The four pilot countries (Greece, the Netherlands, Spain, and the UK) obtained approval for the study from their corresponding Ethics Committee.

7-SEISMO

The intervention has no legal framework and as such, is not enforced. It is publically and privately funded. Private: BNP Paribas Cardiff, Aigües de Barcelona/Agbar, Barça Foundation and Ford. Public: Barcelona, Pineda de Mar, Balaguer and Lleida city councils.

Monitoring

1-The Daily Mile & 2-Active Pauses

At the moment, the monitoring is done through the schools that are inscribed on the platform and participating in the program.

3-PreME-MEMSS

Health, School & Community Service, Barcelona Public Health Agency,

The Technical Secretariat of the Program is in charge of the accompaniment of the enrolled schools throughout the process. Participating schools are given a questionnaire at the beginning of the school year and are administered again at the end of the school year. This way, we can assess specific changes made at the level of the school menu (nutritional) and at the level of changes in sustainability, proximity, etc.

PreME-MEMSS **indicators** were established as key variables for evaluating the quality of the meal plans: fresh fruit for dessert, pulses as a first course, vegetables on the daily menu, fresh food (raw fruit and/or vegetables) in the daily menu, olive oil for dressing, etc. Also, there are indicators of sustainability, such as the presence of organic food, seasonal food or local food.

4-La Mina

The Catalan Public Health Agency (ASPCAT) is responsible for monitoring the overall intervention, with participating health care professionals conducting the evaluation activities (indicators).

5-INFADIMED

The Catalan Institute of Health (L'Institut Català de la Salut) is the government agency responsible for funding and monitoring the intervention, as it is the source of the intervention.

6-SEEDS

The researchers of the study are responsible for monitoring the intervention.

7-SEISMO

The Gasol Foundation is the Foundation that creates, implements, and funds the intervention.

Barriers (categorized as cost/financing constraints, social/cultural constraints, degree of acceptability, other implementation barriers and some explanations)

1-The Daily Mile & 2-Active Pauses

The barriers of both interventions are mainly related with its degree of acceptability.

The first barrier we encounter is that knowledge of the project does not easily reach the schools and, if it does, it has to become a priority to the headmasters of the schools to implement the program; otherwise, its acceptance is difficult. The teachers are also a relevant piece of the puzzle, as their time and mind-set in regards to this kind of activities can be an essential barrier to the success of the program.

Lastly, there might be, from the childcare and school domain, physical activity programs barriers.

3-PReME-MEMSS

There are **cost/financing constraints**, as the program carries an economic cost currently shared between Barcelona City Council and the Barcelona Public Health Agency, as well as the Catalonia Public Health Agency. The coordination of the program is carried out by a Technical Secretary (professionals from an entity that is an expert in sustainable and local food), the review of school menus is carried out by a professional hired for this purpose and we have an expert advisor in nutrition for those issues that are necessary.

There are currently schools enrolled in the program that make certain demands that are not covered by the afore-mentioned cost. Currently, these demands cannot be met (providing local and seasonal food as an incentive, training in kitchens and kitchen reform, dining room scholarships, etc.) and, also, more Dietitian-Nutritionists and public health specialists are needed in order to implement Phase 3 of the menu reviews.

We have also identified **social/cultural constraints**. Society is still not aware of the necessary changes in terms of food that we have to make. This means that sometimes families do not fully understand why certain changes are made to school menus. Students are also reluctant to make certain changes to the menu. On the other hand, cultural customs about the consumption of certain foods can also make it difficult to accept the changes proposed by the program (e.g., children from newly arrived families have different eating habits). Moreover, children are continuously exposed to food marketing and influenced by media.

The **degree of acceptability**, therefore, has been a challenge. Also, it has to be accepted and well-coordinated by the agents involved in the programme (school management, management company, canteen monitors, teachers, families). This coordination and acceptance vary from school to school and can make or break their development.

Other barriers:

- The program does not reach pre-school schools
- Lack of regulation on healthy and sustainable school menus
- Untrained monitoring equipment in children's diet-health
- Sale of unhealthy products at the school environment

4-La Mina

Cost and financing constraints include the increased need for professionals and their time to dedicate to the personalized intervention, preparation of materials, time / training needs for health professionals and stakeholders. Funding structural changes necessary to reduce obesogenic environments i.e. bike lanes, parks, school canteens, etc. are also necessary.

Social/Cultural constraints:

Many families do not perceive childhood obesity as a health problem. La Mina is a neighbourhood that presents a disadvantaged socio-economic situation together with high vulnerability and conflict that requires focused actions. There are many destructured families with a lot of conflicts that "live in the immediacy and with a low level of planning". There are families who may want to change but do not have any sense of aesthetic or health risk at the moment. Unhealthy foods are a "prize for good behavior and/or express that they are "the only luxury the family can offer" compared to other material purchases. These foods are seen as an act of love towards their children.

- Passive positioning and “saviour role” of healthcare professionals: Families are not used to an approach where they and the children are the protagonists of their decisions, so they often expect a process of "classic diet therapy" with an informative/prescriptive model.

Degree of acceptability: The main reason for abandoning the Primary Health Care Center intervention was the lack of interest on the part of the child. According to the parents or guardians, it had to do with the child's lack of limits: “My child doesn’t respect what I say or ask them to do.”, even though all goals were established in mutual agreement with both the child him/herself (and their family).

Other implementation barriers:

- Entry into the community was practically nil during 2021 due to covid-19: the oversaturation of health personnel, as well as the preventive closure, or activity with numerous limiting conditions, of schools as well as of neighbourhood entities. All this paralyzed the start of the scheduled activities.
- The lack of dedicated time for professionals who are overworked.
- Limits related to the poverty index, to the obesogenic environment, to social and cultural determinants, level of neighbourhood conflict
- Lack of coordination and agreed objectives regarding the prevention of obesity in the network of stakeholders (ie donations of unhealthy foods, excursions, etc.)
- Lack of food business networks that offer healthy food...small local grocers disappear from less populated regions in exchange for large supermarket chains (less food sustainability, quality, etc)
- Aggressive marketing of fast food and the ultra-processed industry
- Sustainability of actions after the intervention should be considered at the outset. If a community has been actively engaged, there is a sense of frustration and abandonment after the project ends and actions cease.

5-INFADIMED

Cost/financing: Investment in human resources to replace the nurse who performs the intervention, funding for workshop material both in schools and in communities, funding to promote the program among the community, funding to research the interventions.

Social/cultural: A lot of influence from the outside world, especially in food. We are creating a counterculture in the face of so much promotion of ultra-processed food that is available to the population, with so much marketing. It is one of our main enemies.

Degree of acceptability: There are no limits to the advertising of unhealthy products in the children's population. There is no regulation that prohibits it.

6-SEEDS

Cost/financing: none

Social/cultural: The intervention will be adapted depending on the sociocultural characteristics of each country and population included.

Degree of acceptability: none

Other implementation barriers: COVID-19 pandemic made it difficult to enter schools, and to meet with families for parts of the intervention.

7-SEISMO

Cost/financing: To sustain the investment of private/public funding during a minimum of 6 years per each school is difficult.

Social/cultural: None

Degree of acceptability: None

Other implementation barriers: None

Opportunities for improvement

1-The Daily Mile & 2-Active Pauses

If the Department of Education had more implication in the diffusion of the programmes, they could reach more schools and overcome this first barrier; for example, promote the project on its platforms.

In the same line, we could overcome the barrier by talking to ambassadors (young athletes to who the kids look up to) to promote the project and spread the word.

Once the project reaches the schools, we need to devote more time and efforts to educate their staff about the benefits of the project (for example TDM increases children's ability to learn, so teachers do not "lose time".)

Also, small changes in the curriculum could allow more time for physical activity / active breaks during the school day and facilitate the implementation of these interventions.

3-PreME-MEMSS

First of all, if Education had a regulation that required schools to review their menus from time to time, we would not be limited to working with volunteering centres.

Also, an improvement on the coordination of different institutions and departments to deal with the economic cost of the programme and the specific (unmet) requests of the agents involved would facilitate the progress of the program.

In the same line, there would need to be a specific budget to renovate kitchens and train all staff that participates in the school's lunchtime to know about children's food and health and improve the working conditions of the school cafeteria workers.

The improvement in knowledge of all the school's agents should be disseminated; schools should be in contact with one another and with sustainable food companies, local food, etc.

Raising awareness and education should not end at school, though. Awareness should be raised among the population about the need (for personal health and the health of the planet) to adopt the proposed changes. There should be more communication campaigns, especially aimed at families and children. In school canteens, children should be encouraged to taste different foods on a regular basis, and with that idea in mind, it would be helpful to have practical workshops about food-healthy cuisine included in the school curriculum.

It would also be helpful to have an app/software/program that reviews the menus, both those of early childhood and primary education, and that there are no establishments selling unhealthy products around (within a certain perimeter) schools.

4-La Mina

- The positive final assessment of the sustainability of some activities that were useful for the entities, as well as the possibility of promoting physical activity groups that were self-sustainable. These could be benchmark processes that can be replicated in other communities.
- The comprehensive and personalized approach to the child as part of the Primary Health Care intervention is an enriched prism compared to the usual advice and treatment for childhood obesity. This was possible due to the coordination between different professionals, the dedication of time and adaptation to the characteristics and needs of children and families.

5-INFADIMED

Prohibit the advertising of unhealthy food aimed at children, prohibiting its broadcasting on children's television, or on any channel. City environments could also be improved, with more parks to play in and accessibility to schools.

6-SEEDS

Including different socioeconomic background in the focus groups and co-creation to be able to generalize the intervention to all of us.

Including some online parts to facilitate families' involvement in the project.

Increase the education department relationship, to be able to enter to the school sites without any difficulty and time restriction.

7-SEISMO

Having sustainable financing for the intervention.

Appendix 5. Sweden-specific report of the survey results

1. Survey report on the regulations related to exposure to food advertising and its association with dietary behaviors.

Within this topic we have identified the following list of laws, policies, interventions, and strategies.

1. The Swedish Radio and television Act.
2. The Swedish Marketing Act
3. The Digital Service Act (DSA)
4. Safer Internet Centre Sweden
5. The International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) Advertising and Marketing Communications Code
6. The Audiovisual Media Policy

Type, scale and definition of the regulation

The Swedish Radio and television Act.

A legal framework that outlines the rules and regulations for broadcasting in Sweden. It provides the structure for how television and radio broadcasts should operate, including licensing requirements, content regulations, advertising, and sponsorship guidelines.

The Swedish Marketing Act

Swedish legal framework applied to the entire Swedish society. This Act plays a crucial role in ensuring fair marketing practices and protecting both consumers and businesses in Sweden.

The DSA

A legislative proposal by the European Commission to regulate digital services and online platforms implemented on a European Union (EU) scale.

Safer Internet Centre Sweden

An intervention aimed at ensuring the safety of children and young people online. Scale-wise, the Safer Internet Centre Sweden operates at a national level, focusing on ensuring online safety for children and young people within Sweden. However, the broader initiative spans across the EU, with similar centers existing in all EU countries. These centers collaborate to enhance online safety, share best practices, and collectively address digital challenges.

The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code.

Considered as a strategy, is a set of ethical guidelines developed by the ICC that serve as a global standard for advertising self-regulation.

Audiovisual Media Policy

An EU Policy that aims to shape technological developments, create a level playing field for emerging audiovisual media, preserve cultural diversity, protect children and consumers,

safeguard media pluralism, combat racial and religious hatred, and guarantee the independence of national media regulators.

Main objectives and special considerations taken towards children

The Swedish Radio and television Act.

To provide a legal framework for broadcasting operations. What respects to children the act prohibits advertisements specifically aimed at children under the age of 12 on Swedish public channels

The Swedish Marketing Act

This act's main objectives are to promote the interests of consumers and businesses in connection with the marketing of products and to prevent marketing practices unfair to them. With respect to children, the guidelines titled "Vägledning om marknadsföring riktad till barn och unga" provided by the Swedish Consumer Agency (Konsumentverket) fall under the Marketing Act (Marknadsföringslagen). The objective of these guidelines is to compile the rules and practices that apply to marketing directed at children and young people, as well as minors' ability to enter contracts.

The DSA

The DSA aims to establish a comprehensive regulatory framework for digital services, ensuring their safety, accountability, and transparency. It covers diverse types of online platforms, including social media, e-commerce, and search engines. The strategy balances user rights, innovation, and a safer online environment. When it comes to children, the DSA has the set Child Safety Online; Age-Appropriate Content; Parental Controls; Education and Awareness; Reporting Mechanisms; Privacy Protection; Zero Tolerance on Targeting Ads to Children and teens as specific objectives.

Safer Internet Centre Sweden

The intervention consists of providing knowledge, support, and preventive measures to enhance online safety for children and young people. Its primary objectives include Awareness and education, support and guidance, as well as preventive measures.

The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code

The code's main objectives are to promote high ethical standards, protect consumers, provide a goal standard, inspire self-regulatory structures, and adapt to emerging mediums and participants. The code also provides specific guidelines for marketing directed to children such as marking a cut-off between children (<12) and teens (13-18). The code also emphasizes that advertisers have special responsibilities when marketing to these age groups including not advertising products unsuitable for them in media targeted to them. It also calls for particular care when using certain advertising techniques with children, who are still developing their understanding of commercial communications. The code suggests added privacy precautions, such as obtaining parental consent when collecting information from children.

Audiovisual Media Policy

Its **main objectives** are to create a single EU market for audiovisual services, while also promoting cultural diversity and providing an adequate level of consumer and child protection.

Health outcomes

The regulations addressed in the survey do not specifically address physical health. However, they indirectly influence health outcomes by shaping media content, protecting children, and promoting education. Its impact extends beyond broadcasting to societal well-being. For example, the strict rules of advertising to children including reducing children's exposure to advertisements of unhealthy food and beverages may promote healthier choices leading to better physical health.

Target population, target stake holders and context of implementation

Regulation	Population	Stakeholders	Context of implementation
The Swedish Radio and television Act	Viewers, listeners, and the public.	Children, adolescents, and media literacy educators	Broadcasting and media regulation in Sweden
The Swedish Marketing Act	Consumers and businesses	Consumers; businesses; government agencies; industry associations; legal professionals.	Marketing practices related to TV broadcast, order-based TV, and video sharing platforms in Sweden
The Digital Service Act	Users of digital services	Digital service providers; consumers; goods and services providers; smaller platforms and start-ups; regulatory bodies and authorities; civil society organizations and advocacy groups; tech industry associations and trade groups; academics and researchers; public and citizens.	Implemented across all 27 EU Member States. It involves a phased rollout, collaboration with stakeholders, and the creation of detailed guidelines to ensure its effective application in the digital landscape.
Safer Internet Centre Sweden	Children and young people; parents and guardians; professionals working with children.	The Swedish Agency for the Media (Mediemyndigheten) and the NGO's Bris (Children's Rights in Society) and ECPAT (End Child Prostitution, Child Pornography and Trafficking of Children for Sexual Purposes)	The center is implemented within the context of Sweden. However, its goals align with the EU wide effort to create a safer online environment for everyone.
The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code.	The entire population with special attention directed to more vulnerable groups such as children and teens or those who are involved with new forms of media and marketing.	Advertisers, marketing practitioners, regulators, consumers, self-regulatory bodies, emerging mediums, and those who participate in them	The code is implemented in the context of advertising and marketing communications globally.
Audiovisual Media Policy	All citizens, companies and organizations that use or provide audio-	Media companies, regulatory bodies, consumers, cultural and creative sectors, technology	The entire EU

Regulation	Population	Stakeholders	Context of implementation
	visual or media services in the EU.	companies, environmental groups.	

Co-creation participatory methods

Co-creation participatory methods are pivotal in shaping policies and regulations across various sectors. These methods, which involve collaboration and engagement with diverse stakeholders, are particularly prominent in the Digital Services Act (DSA), the Safer Internet Centre Sweden, and the Audiovisual Media Policy.

In the DSA, co-creation methods are employed to foster multi-stakeholder dialogues and collaborations with platforms. This approach ensures a comprehensive and inclusive policy-making process that considers the perspectives and interests of all relevant parties.

The Safer Internet Centre Sweden leverages these methods to cultivate collaboration, raise awareness, and establish a safer digital environment for children and young people. By involving various stakeholders in the process, the Centre ensures that the policies it develops are responsive to the needs and concerns of its target demographic.

The Audiovisual Media Policy also adopts co-creation methods to regulate stakeholder dialogue and enhance engagement. It encourages policy exchange and cooperation with member states, thereby promoting a harmonized approach to policymaking. Furthermore, it applies proven self-organization and design-thinking principles for co-creation, ensuring that the policies it develops are both innovative and effective.

While the Swedish Radio and Television Act (1996), the Swedish Marketing Act, and the ICC code do not explicitly mention the use of co-creation participatory methods, the nature of these regulations suggests an inherent element of collaboration.

Models of behavioral change

None of the regulations addressed in this report use behavioral change models.

Materials and tools used by the regulations

The implementation of regulations across various sectors involves a diverse array of materials and methods.

Digital Services Act: The DSA employs a comprehensive approach, utilizing public consultations, stakeholder dialogues, research and evidence, collaboration with industry, guidance documents, impact assessments, and legislative acts.

Safer Internet Centre Sweden: This organization uses webinars for professionals and schools, educational resources, media literacy training tools, and cross-sector collaboration to implement its policies.

ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code: While the Code itself is a tool, it also provides supplementary materials such as guides for responsible mobile marketing

communications, a mobile supplement to the ICC Resource guide for self-regulation of interest-based advertising, and frameworks on responsible marketing and communications of alcohol, food, beverage, and environmental marketing communications.

Audiovisual Media Policy: In addition to legislative text, this policy uses EU programs like MEDIA, a legislative strand of the “Creative Europe Program”; regulatory frameworks; guidelines; digital platforms; technological strands; cooperation and dialogue.

While the Swedish Radio and Television Act and the Swedish Marketing Act do not explicitly mention any material beyond legislative text, the nature of these regulations suggests the use of similar methods for their implementation. This highlights the importance of diverse materials and methods in facilitating the effective implementation of regulations.

Duration, level of implementation, governmental subsidy, and target setting.

Regulation	Duration	Level of implementation	Governmental subsidy	Target setting
The Swedish Radio and television Act	Adopted in June 2010 and in to force August 2010. (continuously updated)	National	Supported by the Swedish government	Public settings
The Swedish Marketing Act	Issued in June 2008	National	Operates under the authority of the Swedish government	Public and private settings
The Digital Service Act	Came into force in November 2022 and became applicable since February 2024	EU	Government support within the EU	Public and private settings
Safer Internet Centre Sweden	December 2022 - December 2024	Sweden but aligned with an EU effort	supported by the Swedish government, operated by the Swedish Media Council, which operates under the Ministry of Culture	Public and private settings
The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code.	First introduced in 1937 (continuously updated)	Global	No	Public and private settings
Audiovisual Media Policy	First introduced in 1989 (continuously updated)	EU	Supported by the governments of the EU member states	Public and private settings

Digital tools used for implementation

The Swedish Radio and television Act, as well as the Swedish Marketing Act

Do not rely on specific digital tools for their implementation.

The DSA utilizes digital tools to enforce regulations, enhance transparency, and protect user rights in the digital landscape. **Safer Internet Centre Sweden** employs several digital tools and resources to enhance online safety for children and young people such as the awareness center; a helpline; a hotline, youth panels, and the Betterinternetforkids.eu platform.

The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code uses digital tools to provide free online courses on ethical marketing, updated implementation guides. The ICC also considers emerging digital marketing and advertising practices such as AI-enabled marketing, market influencers, vloggers, and data analytics.

Audiovisual Media Policy utilizes digital platforms, interactive tools, media data spaces virtual and augmented reality tools as well as EU supported innovative tools.

Legal support, enforcement, and funding

Regulation	Legal support	Enforcement	Funding
The Swedish Radio and television Act	Officially known as SFS 2010:696, this Act serves as the legal framework	By the Swedish Press and Broadcasting Authority	Public and private sources
The Swedish Marketing Act	Is a legal framework established by the Swedish government to regulate marketing practices.	By the Consumer Ombudsman (Konsumentombudsman, KO)	Swedish government
The Digital Service Act	Establishes a layered framework of responsibilities targeting diverse types of online intermediary services in the EU	Collaborative effort between national authorities and the European Commission within EU	EUs overall budget
Safer Internet Centre Sweden	Supportive framework that includes both legal and organizational components	Statens medieråd (the Swedish Media Council); NGO (BRIS and ECPAT) in Collaboration with the EU-Wide Framework	Currently co-funded by the European Commission under the Digital Europe Program.
The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code.	Global backbone for all local self-regulatory bodies in the advertising and marketing industry.	In Sweden, the Code is applied by the Reklamombudsmannen (RO) and the Jury Reklamombudsmannens opinionsnämnd (RON) when reviewing advertising	Private founding
Audiovisual Media Policy	Supported by several articles of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (Articles 167, 173,28,30,34,45-62, 101-109, 114, 165,166 and 207)	Shared EU responsibility	Public founding through Founded through the MEDIA strand of the Creative Europe program.

Monitoring

The Swedish Radio and television Act.

The Swedish Press and Broadcasting Authority plays a pivotal role in monitoring and enforcing the Swedish Radio and Television Act (1996). Their responsibilities include:

- *Issuing licenses to broadcasters:* Ensuring compliance with licensing requirements.
- *Verifying content:* The Authority ensures that radio and television programs adhere to broadcasting regulations.
- *Overseeing compliance:* They closely monitor these platforms to ensure adherence to regulations.

The Swedish Marketing Act

The Swedish Marketing Act (Marknadsföringslagen) is monitored through various mechanisms to ensure compliance and fair marketing practices:

- *Consumer Ombudsman (Konsumentombudsman, KO):* The Consumer Ombudsman is responsible for enforcing the Act. They investigate potential violations, issue warnings, and take legal action against non-compliant businesses.
- *Self-Regulation and Industry Associations:* Industry associations and self-regulatory bodies play a role in monitoring marketing practices. They establish codes of conduct and guidelines for businesses to follow.
- *Complaints and Reporting:* Consumers, competitors, or other stakeholders can report violations to the Consumer Ombudsman. Complaints trigger investigations and potential legal actions.
- *Digital Tools and Data Analysis:* used to monitor online advertising, track compliance, and detect potential violations. Data analysis helps identify patterns and trends related to marketing practices.
- *Legal Proceedings:* may be initiated against businesses that violate the Act. Courts assess cases, issue fines, and ensure compliance.

The Digital Service Act (DSA)

The DSA is monitored by both the European Commission and national authorities within the EU. The indicators used for monitoring are a mix of quantitative and qualitative indicators to monitor platforms' adherence to regulations and promote a safer digital environment. Such as user number reporting, transparency reporting templates, supervision fee calculation, monitoring of content moderation practices, impact assessment indicators, user rights and compiling mechanisms.

Safer Internet Centre Sweden

Is monitored by the Swedish Media Council and two NGOs (BRIS and ECPAT). The tools used to monitor its implementation are a comprehensive approach that combines data, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and adaptability.

The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code

In Sweden, the organizations responsible for monitoring its application, Reklamombudsmannen (RO) and the Jury Reklamombudsmannens opinionsnämnd (RON). The indicators used for monitoring are not specified in the code.

Audiovisual Media Policy

The organism responsible to monitor this policy are the European commission; National regulatory bodies (in Sweden the Swedish Press and Broadcasting Authority); European Regulators group for audiovisual media services; Media pluralism monitor. The tools used for monitoring are:

- *Country of Origin, Jurisdiction, Derogation, and Circumvention*: These indicators assess the application of the country-of-origin principle and its exceptions, the amendments made by Directive (EU) 2018/1808, the application of the temporary derogation procedure, the application of the anti-circumvention procedure, and the effects of the 2018 revision in applying the exceptional procedures.
- *Rules on Video-Sharing-Platforms (VSPs)*: These indicators evaluate the response to a changed content dissemination landscape by expanding the scope of the AVMSD, obligations for VSP providers and implementation, and cooperation between regulatory authorities.
- *Rules on European Works*: These indicators monitor the system of promoting European works, the amendments by Directive 2018 and the new framework for on-demand services, and compliance with different promotion obligations.
- *Consistency and Coherence*: These indicators assess the interplay with other legislative acts.
- *Media Pluralism Monitor (MPM)*: The MPM assesses risk scores for various indicators and sub-indicators, grouped as Low (0 – 33%), Medium (34-66%), and High (67-100%).
- *Green Indicators*: The Creative Europe Monitoring Guide for Program Greening proposes green indicators to measure the program's progress, but also to feed back into the European Green Deal objectives post-2027.

Barriers

Swedish Radio and Television Act (1996)

There are notable barriers related to the Swedish Radio and Television Act (1996) such as:

- *Limited Scope for Digital Platforms*: While the Act primarily focuses on traditional broadcasting channels (television and radio), it does not specifically cover digital sharing platforms. These platforms, such as YouTube, operate in a different landscape and may require separate regulations to address their unique challenges.
- *Cross-Border Satellite Channels*: Satellite channels broadcasted from other countries are not subject to the same Swedish advertising ban. This lack of authority makes it challenging to enforce restrictions on children's advertisements when they originate from foreign channels.
- *Emerging Technologies*: The Act was established in 1996, and since then, technology has evolved significantly. New media formats, streaming services, and online content platforms have emerged, necessitating continuous adaptation of regulations to keep pace with technological advancements.
- *Balancing Freedom of Expression*: Striking the right balance between protecting minors and ensuring freedom of expression remains a challenge. While the Act aims

to shield children from harmful content, it must also respect individuals' rights to express themselves through the media.

- *Enforcement and Monitoring:* Ensuring compliance with the Act requires robust monitoring mechanisms. The Swedish Press and Broadcasting Authority faces the task of overseeing a diverse media landscape, including both traditional and digital channels.

Moreover, the Swedish Radio and Television Act (1996) does not specifically mention food advertisements. However, it focuses on broadcasting regulations, licensing requirements, and content standards for traditional channels like television and radio. While the Act does not directly address food advertising, other legislation and self-regulatory mechanisms may apply.

The Swedish Marketing Act

The barriers that the Swedish marketing act faces are related to costs, taxes, and competitive regulations.

Food advertising is not specifically addressed within the context of the Swedish Marketing Act (Marknadsföringslagen) however food advertisements must follow the act guidelines, such as: Protection of Minors (Advertising to minors (persons under 18) is strictly regulated); Prohibited advertisement methods (subliminal messaging, spam, direct marketing); prohibited and controlled advertising; and product restrictions.

DSA

The DSA faces specific barriers related to content targeted at children such as:

- *Balancing Protection and Innovation:* Striking a balance between safeguarding children from harmful content and allowing age-appropriate innovation is complex.
- *Defining "Child" and "Teen":* The DSA must define clear age categories that determine if the minor is a child or a teenager to apply targeted advertising restrictions effectively.
- *Enforcement and Monitoring:* Ensuring compliance with ad targeting rules requires robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms.
- *Adaptability to Evolving Platforms:* New forms of content and advertising emerge, necessitating ongoing updates and adjustments.

Moreover, while the DSA prohibits targeted advertising to minors, there are a few exceptions and nuances to consider:

- *Contextual Advertising:* The DSA allows for contextual advertising, which is based on the content of the webpage or app rather than individual user profiles. For example, if a child is browsing a website about educational games, contextual ads related to educational toys or games may still appear (This means that **Sponsored content** can still be targeted to children within the framework of the DSA).
- *Parental Consent:* If a platform obtains explicit parental consent, it may show targeted ads to minors. However, this consent process must be transparent and comply with data protection regulations.
- *Age Verification:* Platforms can use age verification mechanisms to determine whether a user is a minor. If a user is verified as an adult, targeted ads may be shown.

- *Public Health Campaigns:* The DSA recognizes the importance of public health campaigns. Ads related to health and safety, such as vaccination awareness or healthy eating, may still be targeted to minors.
- *Non-Commercial Content:* Content that is not directly commercial, such as public service announcements or educational material, is exempt from these restrictions.

Safer Internet Centre Sweden

This intervention faces several challenges, including raising awareness among parents and professionals, bridging the digital divide, adapting to rapid technological changes, ensuring privacy protection, coordinating multi-stakeholder efforts, evaluating impact, and navigating legal complexities. Balancing safety with privacy rights and addressing emerging online risks are critical considerations. Moreover, this intervention does not include specific details about food advertising or advertising to kids.

The ICC Advertising and Marketing Communications Code

The implementation of the ICC Code faces several barriers such as:

- *Awareness and Understanding:* Not all businesses, especially smaller ones, may be aware of the ICC Code or fully understand its guidelines. This can lead to non-compliance, not out of disregard for the Code, but simply due to lack of knowledge.
- *Diverse and Evolving Marketing Practices:* The marketing landscape is constantly evolving with recent technologies and platforms. Keeping the Code up-to-date and relevant to these changes can be challenging.
- *Global Applicability vs Local Context:* While the ICC Code is designed to be globally applicable, there can be challenges in interpreting and applying it in distinct cultural and legal contexts.
- *Enforcement:* The ICC Code is self-regulatory, meaning businesses are expected to adhere to it voluntarily. However, enforcement can be challenging, especially without the backing of legislation.
- *Resource Constraints:* Self-regulatory bodies that oversee the implementation of the Code may face resource constraints, which can limit their effectiveness.
- *Digital Complexity:* With the rise of digital marketing, there are complexities around data privacy, consent, and transparency that can pose challenges to the implementation of the Code.

The Audiovisual and Media Policy

The Audiovisual and Media Policy of the European Union faces several barriers such as:

- *Technological Changes:* Rapid technological changes, such as the rise of digital platforms and services, pose a challenge to the policy. The policy needs to adapt to these changes and ensure that it remains relevant and effective.
- *Diverse Media Landscape:* The media landscape in the EU is diverse, with different languages, cultures, and traditions. This diversity can make it challenging to implement a uniform policy across all member states.
- *Regulatory Challenges:* The policy faces regulatory challenges, such as the need to balance the free movement of services with the protection of cultural diversity.

- *Competition with Global Players:* European media companies face stiff competition from global players, especially those based in the US. This competition can make it difficult for European companies to compete on a level playing field.
- *Legal Constraints:* The policy operates within the constraints of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which does not provide for any direct powers in audiovisual and media policy.
- *Digital and Green Transitions:* The policy aims to help industry embrace the digital and green transitions. However, these transitions can pose challenges, such as the need for investment and the development of new skills.

Areas of opportunity

Most of the barriers can be addressed through continuous education, regular updates, collaboration with local regulatory bodies, and promotion of the benefits.

Our survey report has identified an intriguing opportunity in the realm of digital food advertisements targeted at children and young audiences. These advertisements play a significant role in shaping the dietary patterns, behaviors, and food choices of children and adolescents. Currently, the regulations addressing food advertisements are rather vague, and the precise extent of children's exposure to food advertisements remains uncertain. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of the exposure as well as the influence that food content as well as food advertisement have in children and teenagers is necessary to prevent chronic diseases such as obesity related cancers and improve the overall health of these young individuals.

The impact of such a study extends beyond academic interest. As a public health initiative, it could foster significant outcomes that may inform and shape our current policies. This endeavor underscores the importance of understanding and regulating digital food advertisements, given their profound influence on our younger generations.

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2. Survey report on the European school fruit vegetables and milk scheme

The European school fruit, vegetables and milk scheme is a program that operates within a policy framework. The scheme is implemented on a European Union (EU) scale and provides funding and support for the distribution of milk, fruits, and vegetables in educational institutions across EU member states. Its primary goal is to encourage nutritious dietary choices and raise awareness about agriculture and food production processes.

Main objectives and special considerations taken in Sweden

The main objectives of the European Union (EU) School Fruit, Vegetables, and Milk Scheme are as follows:

- *Promoting Healthy Eating Habits:* The scheme aims to encourage children to consume more fruits, vegetables, and milk. By providing these nutritious foods in schools, it promotes healthy dietary choices among young learners.
- *Educating About Agriculture and Food Production:* Through the distribution of fruits, vegetables, and milk, the program also educates students about agriculture and food production processes. It helps them understand where their food comes from and fosters an appreciation for farming.
- *Enhancing Overall Well-Being:* By incorporating these food items into school routines, the scheme contributes to the overall well-being of children. Proper nutrition supports physical health, cognitive development, and concentration in the classroom.
- *EU Funding and Cooperation:* The scheme operates with EU funding and cooperation. It aligns with broader EU policies related to agriculture, health, and education.

While Sweden has previously utilized EU support for school milk, it has not yet implemented the school fruit component. However, on the 5th of February of 2024 the Swedish government aired a press release entrusting the Swedish Board of Agriculture (Jordbruksverket) with the task of implementing support for fruit in schools starting from the school year 2025/2026. As part of this assignment, the Swedish Board of Agriculture will conduct a review of the school milk support to ensure effective implementation of the entire EU school program, including the inclusion of fruits.

Health outcomes

The scheme has several health-related objectives and outcomes:

- *Promoting Healthy Diets:* The scheme encourages children to consume fresh fruits, vegetables, and milk. By providing these foods in schools, it aims to improve dietary habits and overall health.
- *Reducing Obesity:* The program contributes to efforts in reducing overweight and obesity. It promotes the consumption of fresh or processed fruits, vegetables, milk,

and selected milk products in line with national dietary recommendations and food-based dietary guidelines.

- *Educational Measures:* Beyond food distribution, the scheme supports educational activities. These include lessons, farm visits, school gardens, tasting workshops, and cooking workshops. The goal is to reconnect children to agriculture and teach them about healthy eating habits. Topics like local food chains, organic farming, sustainable production, and food waste may also be covered.
- *Visibility and Evaluation:* Funding is available for information activities to ensure the visibility of the scheme. Monitoring and evaluation help assess its proper functioning and impact.

Target Population, target stakeholders and context of implementation

Population: Schoolchildren (from nursery school up to secondary school levels) across EU member states. To this day most of the children participating in the scheme belong to the 6-10 years old age group.

Stakeholders: Educational institutions, National authorities, Farmers and producers, Parents and guardians, health professionals and EU institutions.

Context of implementation: Implemented (up to some degree) across the 27 countries belonging to the EU. Sweden did not use the support for fruit, only used the milk supplement.

Co-creation participatory methods

School Fruit, Vegetables, and Milk Scheme does not explicitly use co-creation participatory methods as a primary approach. However, it involves collaboration among various stakeholders, including educational institutions, national authorities, farmers, parents, and health professionals. These stakeholders collectively contribute to the successful implementation of the program. While the scheme emphasizes educational activities and awareness, direct co-creation with students and parents is not a central feature of its design.

Models of behavioral change

The implementation of the scheme does not apply a model of behavioral change.

Materials and tools used by the regulations

The EU School Scheme utilizes a combination of fresh produce distribution, educational activities, and information measures to promote healthy eating habits among schoolchildren.

Duration, level of implementation, governmental subsidy, and target setting

The program has been applicable since 2017 and is subsidized by the European Union. The scheme primarily targets public educational institutions.

Digital tools used for implementation

The scheme's implementation does not explicitly rely on digital tools as a central feature.

Legal support, enforcement, and funding

Enforcement of the program is considered a collaborative effort between EU institutions, national authorities, schools, and various stakeholders.

The program receives EU funding, and the following regulations are their legal framework:

Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013, Articles 22 to 25, and Annex V;

- Council Regulation (EU) No 1370/2013, Article 5, and Annex I;
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/39, with rules for uniform implementation of the scheme.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/40, with additional specific rules for the scheme's implementation.

Monitoring

At the EU level, the European Commission oversees the implementation and monitoring of the scheme by collaborating with national authorities and maintaining the data portal to monitor and evaluate the EU School Scheme's effectiveness across member states.

In Sweden, the Swedish Board of Agriculture (Jordbruksverket) is responsible for monitoring and overseeing the implementation of the program.

Barriers

- The implementation of the scheme has been very heterogeneous, which means that EU students do not benefit equally from it.
- The lack of continuity in the execution, as well as the sparse number of days of fruits and vegetables deliveries, could limit its potential benefits.
- Administrative burden.
- Covid-19 Pandemic impact.
- Fruit types to be distributed.
- Coordination of food distribution and food waste.
- Raising awareness within the school and the student community.
- Connection with school nurses.
- Long term scalability.

Areas of opportunity

- To design and implement a technology-based system for the onsite distribution of fruits (mainly) and vegetables in Swedish schools.
- Focus on automated monitoring of fruit/vegetable distribution to the end users and association with real-world dietary habit changes.
- Identify and test the pragmatic school and student needs with regards to:
 - Preferred deployment parameters at the school.
 - Student awareness raising for health-benefits, short and long-term.

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3. Survey report on the school meal system

In Sweden, the free school meal system is expansive, and very well-established. It was originally introduced for primary schools and has its roots in the late 19th century. It is now a legal right for all primary school children. It is not a legal right for other age groups. Despite this, it is firmly integrated into all pre-schools too, however it is only partly integrated into secondary schools. There is therefore potential for expansion at these older age groups.

All primary school pupils (ages 6-15) are legally entitled to education, including materials, free of charge. Since 2011 this also includes “nutritious school meals”.

Brief background

- 1946: National policy is introduced to subsidise meals if local authorities chose to provide them
- 1970s: Implementation of school lunches nationally is now widespread
- 1998: Education Act 1997 comes into force; meals are to be provided to all, ‘free of charge’.
- 2011: Education Act 2010 comes into force and adds that meals should be ‘nutritious’.

Upper secondary schools are covered by same Education Act. Upper secondary schools (pupils 16-19 years of age) are legally entitled to education, including materials, that is free of charge. Meals however do *not* have to be provided (at a cost or otherwise). Many upper secondary schools provide meals anyway but some choose to provide vouchers that can be used in nearby restaurants.

School meals in primary schools are generally nutritious, often more so than other meals consumed (1) so this failure to fully implement it for all pupils is a missed opportunity to improve dietary habits.

Main objectives and special considerations taken in Sweden

The main purpose of chapter 10, paragraph 8 in the Education Act is to ensure that education and all necessary equipment is free of charge for primary school children. A school meal is deemed necessary in this age group.

No further clarification of ‘nutritious’ is made in the legislation but an interpretation by the School Inspection Agency, who technically is the government agency that follows up implementation of school law, concluded that meals should be in line with Swedish/Nordic nutritional recommendations, and that schools should include meals in their systematic routines for quality control. The School Inspection Agency does not, however, follow up school meal nutritional quality.

Non-binding guidelines for school meals for all ages/school types are produced by the Swedish Food Agency, a government agency. Guidelines were first issued in 2007, major revision was published in 2013, minor revision 2023 (2).

The guidelines state that meals are expected to meet nutritional recommendations over a four-week period, and include general information about foods to promote, but no standards or rules to follow. A Swedish school lunch in primary/upper secondary school consists of a cooked meal, a salad buffet and crispbread with spread and milk/water. Deep-fried foods have never been a feature, nor have desserts or soft drinks. In the majority of schools, a choice of two or more warm meals is offered, and these days one of those options is very often vegetarian. Food is prepared freshly, either on-site (by local authority or private catering) at a nearby school or at a central local authority kitchen. School cafeterias are common, but while the offering is generally less healthy it is not free of charge, and vending machines are very rare in primary schools. In primary schools, pupils are not permitted to bring food from home, but teenagers may generally leave the school premises.

In upper secondary schools many schools provide meals. Pupils can skip these of course and many can leave the premises. Some provide vouchers instead for nearby restaurants.

Health outcomes

No health outcomes are mentioned in the legislation.

The national guidelines say "School meals should provide the energy and nutrition that pupils need to grow, develop and be able to concentrate and learn during the school day. Schools also have an educational opportunity to show pupils what healthy food is, thus providing a foundation for good eating habits in the future."

Target Population, target stakeholders and context of implementation

Population:

Children aged 6-15, attending primary school, grades 1 to 12 which are compulsory – are fully covered, legal requirement.

All children in preschools (18 months to 6 years) - fully covered, praxis, not a legal requirement.

Upper secondary schools (pupils 16-19 years of age) - are not yet fully covered.

Stakeholders:

- Local authorities, who are responsible for running all public schools.
- Local authority catering staff who may work at schools or in centralised kitchens.
- Companies and foundations that run private schools. [The legislation applies equally to private schools.]
- State agencies, such as Swedish Food Agency and Swedish Board of Education (who support schools).
- Parents and guardians.
- Teachers and school health care staff.

Implementation:

School meals are implemented in all 290 local authorities, in all primary schools. The level of implementation in secondary schools is unknown.

Co-creation participatory methods

A successful school meal programmed involves collaboration among various stakeholders, including educational institutions, national authorities, parents, and food service dietitians and caterers. While the guidelines emphasizes educational activities connected to school meals and raising awareness about the importance of foods and mealtimes to health and the overall school day, direct co-creation with students and parents is not a central feature of its design. Many schools however have a food council where pupil, catering staff and educators or school leaders meet to discuss issues.

Models of behavioral change

The implementation of the school meals does not apply a model of behavioral change.

Materials and tools used by the regulations

n/a

Duration, level of implementation, governmental subsidy, and target setting

- Since requirement on free education and free nutritious school meals for primary schools but free education only for upper primary schools, 2011-07-01.
- Since requirement on free education and school meals for primary schools but free education only for upper primary schools, 1998-07-01.
- Legislation is national.
- Implementation is local as local authorities/municipalities (n=290) run schools.

Digital tools used for implementation

The school meal implementation does not explicitly rely on digital tools as a central feature.

Legal support, enforcement, and funding

The legal framework is the legislation Skollag [Education Act] (2010:800), soon to be replaced by Skollag [Education Act] (2023:951)

Enforcement of the program is considered a collaborative effort between national authorities, local authorities, schools.

School meals are funded entirely by public funding. Local authorities receive money from the national government but also from local taxes to cover the running of schools (even private ones).

Monitoring

- No formal monitoring.
- The School Inspection Agency is the government agency that follows up implementation of school law. They have published a report explaining that they

interpret the law to mean that meals should be in line with Swedish/Nordic nutritional recommendations, and that schools should include meals in their systematic routines for quality control. The School Inspection Agency does not, however, follow up school meal nutritional quality during routine inspections.

- Primary schools that choose to can use a web-based self-monitoring tool available since 2012 provide some indicators of % serving nutritious menus, percent having difficulty meeting requirements for certain nutrients, percent serving more than one dish per day etc (3).

Barriers

- The cost of food and electricity has risen significantly in recent months/years and local authorities are finding it necessary to reduce food budgets. The consequences for health are unknown.
- It is considered appropriate to serve meals that are not 100% in line with nutritional guidelines in primary schools if it means that pupils are happier and are not going hungry, and there is less food waste. It is a tough balancing act to change menus while still ensuring that pupils eat.
- It is deemed acceptable that pupils over a certain age can leave the premises.
- It is deemed acceptable that these pupils have choice and access to fast food restaurants/other establishments selling unhealthy foods and beverages (i.e., convenience stores, etc.).
- It is deemed acceptable to provide vouchers without oversight to upper secondary pupils as many of them are legally adults.

Areas of opportunity

- To demonstrate the effect of issuing vouchers in upper secondary schools on school lunch quality.
- To demonstrate how lunch quality, whether school provided or vouchers, is affected by the food establishments and advertising in the local environment surrounding upper secondary schools.

References

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